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*Appraising emotiveness in translations of key
political speeches amid the Tunisian Revolution*

By

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In The Name of God Most Gracious Most Merciful

I dedicate this dissertation to the souls of the Tunisians who were killed during the Tunisian revolution (17/12/2010 – 14/01/2011), as well as to the victims of Ben Ali's regime (1987-2011).

In dedication to my Mother and Father, whose inspiration shines through every page of this dissertation.

National Anthem of Tunisia
"حماة الحمى" "Humat Al Hima" (Defenders of the Homeland)

O defenders of the Homeland!
Rally around to the glory of our time!
The blood surges in our veins,
We die for the sake of our land.

Let the heavens roar with thunder
Let thunderbolts rain with fire.
Men and youth of Tunisia,
Rise up for her might and glory.
No place for traitors in Tunisia,
Only for those who defend her!
We live and die loyal to Tunisia,
A life of dignity and a death of glory.

As a nation we inherited
Arms like granite towers.
Holding aloft our proud flag flying,
We boast of it, it boasts of us,
Arms that achieve ambitions and glory,
Sure to realize our hopes,
Inflict defeat on foes,
Offer peace to friends.

When the people will to live,
Destiny must surely respond.
Oppression shall then vanish.
Fetters are certain to break.

Words by: Mustafa Sadik Al-Rafii and Aboul-Qacem Echebbi
Adopted: 1957, replaced 1958, restored 1987

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Chapter one: Introduction

1.1 Arrangement of the introductory chapter

This chapter deals with five main sections. Part 1 will talk about the reasons that convinced me to embark on such miscellaneous topic due to its stretched parameters and variables. Part 2 will show the limitations and the periphery of this research. This will be followed by Part 3 which will briefly discuss the major problems of this study, guided by the various views of translation scholars and theorists dealing with translation quality assessment of political speeches with an eye on persuasion and emotiveness. This chapter also outlines the major research questions of the dissertation. Part 4 will communicate knowledge to the reader of those who would profit from the research especially future trainee and translation evaluators. The final section will layout the general plan of the dissertation and will sketch its main sections and chapters, with the aim of trying to find solutions to the research questions by analyzing the data, probing the findings, and sampling the answers.

1.2 Purpose of the dissertation

The main issue the study is to assess the ST-TT analysis strategies employed by the translator to convey the specific meanings of the STs into the TTs. The aim of this study is to investigate the competences needed for future translators and trainees, this investigation shall take House's Translation Quality Assessment (TQA) model as a springboard of argumentation and analyses which shall be implemented by translators working on political speeches. The area under discussion of this dissertation is translation of political discourse from the perspective of translation quality assessment focusing on the strategies employed by the translator to convey emotive meanings of the source texts. Notably, this dissertation scrutinizes the translation of a particular type of political discourse which is inner-state political speeches, specifically, delivered political speeches by President Ben Ali in Tunisia before being overthrown.

The dissertation capitalizes on translation of political speeches, in which the speaker is the head of a state that uses MSA (Modern Standard Arabic) that is heavily nuanced with the

Tunisian dialect. The main purpose of this paper is to examine the ST-TT analysis strategies employed by the translator and the challenges posed by the speeches; also the focus will be on translation of persuasion and emotiveness used in Arabic political speeches as a tool of communication rhetoric to gain political goals. The analysis of the data (The Tunisian president's political speeches are taken as a sample) will mainly depend on assessing how emotiveness is rendered while translating the speeches with focus on the loss and gains in translation as well as the strategies employed by the translator.

The purpose of the research is to establish whether there appears a broad-spectrum strategic approach to assess and analyse authentic translations of political speeches. In addition, the dissertation focuses on translations of political speeches that were translated from Arabic into English where the target audience shall be political analysts, foreign embassies and mass media. Throughout the study, detailed ST-TT analysis and assessment of how emotive expressions and manipulation are translated from Arabic into English, while maintaining the persuasive content of the source text. Also a description of actual ways of translating the persuasive and emotive expressions accurately and faithfully into English will be explained.

1.3 Scope of the Study

This study aims to appraise the translations of three separate political speeches according to a number of distinct parameters. According to Larose “the creation of truly comprehensive TQA grid or model is probably impossible because of the numbers of parameters or criteria, the complexity of their relationships and the time and resources required to implement it, accordingly any grid is necessarily reductionist and based on the most relevant parameters and criteria” (1998:175 cited in Williams 2004:11). The study is interested with the phase of source text and target analysis.

The nature of the issue is purely academic and theoretical since the subject matter is an endeavour to investigate a relevant model to the evaluation of the translation of political speeches, primarily with focus on House's model of translation quality assessment, and in secondary position Reiss' text typology and Vermeer's Skopos theory. The topic of TQA has been extensively discussed in the literature, here it is imperative to delimit my paper to the ST-TT analysis and procedures adopted by translators of political speeches,

questioning the motive that prompted them to choose such strategies to overcome the difficulties they face while translating emotiveness and persuasive expressions.

The discussion within this dissertation shall be mainly descriptive that is to say individual translation products are studied in order to describe and explain the specific problems encountered and the strategies employed for their more or less appropriate solution, the main aim is to develop awareness for the ST-TT analysis norms that a translator should abide by in political speeches translation. The aim is to examine the specific translations of the speeches; this will be a contribution to research on the translation of political speeches.

The thesis uses a corpus of various speeches as data collected mostly through web sites of news networks and embassies. The corpus texts include: three political speeches delivered by the ousted Tunisian president during the Tunisian revolution also known as the revolution of dignity and freedom; three Arabic transcripts of the speeches were translated into English.

1.4 Layout of problems and Main research questions:

It has been argued that TQA models have not yet developed a methodical critical apparatus for the assessment and comparison of source and target language in political discourse. It is asserted that such an analytical instrument must extend to social, cultural, historical, hermeneutical and political contextual traits of source and target texts in a logical mode. This is essential for the perception of how the correlation and the interchange between such contextual features affect target texts and its production. Here the study investigates how House's model, Vermeer's Skopos theory and Reiss text typology can collectively bring a starting point for future translators and trainees a model that systematically produce an equivalent quality translation as a product.

Every translation project is a balancing process achieved by construction of a target text under the constant restraint of a source text. While trying to find the closest equivalents in the target language, the translator must always have an eye on the source text in order to confirm the adequacy of the equivalents (Kade, 1964: 137)

Research questions:

- The aim of the study is to assess how political discourse is translated with focus on the emotive and expressive aspect of the speeches, how and to what extent the translator managed to transfer the expressive side of the speeches? How can he use political discourse analysis as a springboard to reach a quality translation?
- By applying House's quality assessment approach, and identifying the intra- and extra-textual features used as well as the procedures applied in translations of political speeches, this dissertation strives to answer the question of how emotiveness in political speeches are translated with quality?
- How genre/register analysis is used by the translator to keep with the pace of changes in these speeches knowing that these speeches were published in a state sponsored press agency Tunis Afrique Presse (TAP) (Arabic: وكالة تونس إفريقيا للأنباء)?
- What are the ST/TT analysis strategies the translator of political discourse follows? Taking into account the translation issues connected to emotiveness and persuasion; to what extent the translator succeeded to convey manipulation, emotiveness and persuasion to the English readers?
- To what extent can House's model of TQA account for register and genre analysis to produce a quality translation of political discourse?
- What are the challenges that faced the translator of the political speeches of President Ben Ali during the Tunisian revolution?

1.5 Practical benefit of the dissertation:

The purpose of this study is to update future translators with the basic translation oriented ST-TT analysis of evaluation needed for an equivalent acceptable translation of political speeches, so that when they start the process of translation they will have in mind a set of criteria and ST-TT analysis approaches that are required for a quality translation.

Here the study strives to give an overview in the relationship between strategies and ST-TT analysis applied on TQA models with the use of Tunisian political speeches as a case study. Also, the study is trying to investigate why political speeches are challenging for

translators in terms of conveying and transferring the emotive side of the speeches between two different cultures. The English speeches shall be used in a comparative genre/ register analysis with the Arabic source texts, for the purpose of determining the genre conventions in both the Tunisian political culture and English political culture.

The purpose of this paper shall be proven through using real-life political speeches delivered by the ousted president Ben Ali, with the use of ST and TT analyses and comparisons. The following dissertation sheds light on TQA theoretical models of analysis that was developed by Juliane House, Anna Trosborg. Such models are used in translator's training and evaluation. These models include a detailed textual analysis of the source text, an analysis of the target text and the communicative situation of the translation, and an analysis of the micro- and macro strategies used.

1.6 Organization of the dissertation:

The thesis first examines how to define concepts such as political texts, emotiveness, translation oriented ST-TT analysis and quality in political speeches translations. The purpose of this theoretical discussion is to review Housian model that can be used to describe and characterize evaluation and assessment of translation. This model is then applied to the source texts and target texts in order to determine the way emotiveness is expressed within this genre.

The thesis also examines how the concept of translation quality assessment can be defined, and what are the relevant steps needed for such evaluation of the corpus at hand. This highlights how TQA models can be used by translators in determining the strategies and procedures needed for a quality translation. Furthermore, the thesis establishes that House's TQA model is indeed valid for the purpose of the thesis, because such prior theoretical conceptualization and pragmatic knowledge are crucial competences for translators to produce quality translation.

The overall aim of this project is to engage with emotiveness in political translation and to reflect on what is involved previous to and later than, as well as throughout, the translating process, particularly in relation to translation quality assessment of target texts and providing the intended reader with a quality translation. How translation-oriented ST and

TT analysis encompass the shift in the way emotiveness and persuasion is expressed in both cultures.

In the concluding analysis and evaluation, the translations are contrasted to the source texts through the use of Trosborg's model for ST-TT analysis. The investigation implies a clear pattern in the procedures adopted in all the translations. Although, the study finds no indications that the translations are tailored to English political conventions, yet finds indications of a deliberate strategy to re-create the rhetorical effect of the original Arabic speeches.

The final conclusion will deal with the results that suggest given competences to translate political speeches taking into consideration several criteria and norms to reach such an elevated standard of translation. If we answer these research questions and confirm the afore-motined research questions the study should establish a solid basis for the improvement of translation training, practicing, quality, efficiency and commercial success. Nonetheless, for the reason the corpus was selected, these findings can only be assumed to be valid for translations that are used by the media.

Chapter two: Assessing translation of emotiveness in political discourse

2.1 Introduction

This chapter will inspect how textual-oriented analysis of emotive political discourse and translation assessment interchange to produce a quality translation, and how it is crucial for translators of political discourse (PD) to use discourse analysis (DA) as a tool for a quality translation of emotive expressions. Likewise this chapter examines concepts such as political speeches as a linguistic activity and political concepts. This will be followed by a brief review of emotiveness in Arabic language which is discussed in relation to translation of political discourse; this part will investigate emotiveness in the political speeches with an eye to translation. Also this chapter proposes to review and discuss translation quality assessment models that take text, not a sentence as the ultimate aim of analysis. The purpose of this theoretical discussion is to adopt a model that can be used to describe and characterize evaluation and assessment of emotiveness in political speeches translation. The chapter also examines the concept of translation quality assessment and the strategies needed to produce an adequate translation of emotive political speeches, and explore the relevant criteria necessary for such evaluation. This highlights how (TQA) models can be used by translators in determining the required strategies and procedures for a quality translation. In addition to that, this chapter reviews the relationship between (TQA) and (PD) to explore the challenges that face the translator of political discourse with focus on emotiveness and persuasion.

2.2 Political Discourse & translation

2.2.1 Politics as discourse

“Political discourse can be simply marked as the discourse of politicians, i.e. their text and talk, and their professional activities. The topics discussed usually come from public events that require collective decision-making, policies, regulations or legislation” (Van Dijk 2001. 4).

How can politics be defined? On the one hand, politics is viewed as a struggle for power between those who seek to assert and maintain their power and those who seek to resist it. On the other hand, politics is viewed as cooperation, as the practices and institutions that a society has for resolving clashes of interest over money, influence, liberty and the like (Paul Chilton 2004:3). Here we are interested in the first definition of politics (politics as a struggle for power) since President Ben Ali was giving his speeches in times of a revolution while he was delivering his speeches to maintain power. Hence politicians use language as a means of persuasion, manipulation and control.

Schäffner distinguishes between two types of political discourse which includes inner-state and inter-state discourse, here the study is interested with the inner-state political discourse, each individual speech is embedded in a wider political discourse, the texts thus show a high degree of intertextuality (cf. de Beaugrande & Dressler, 1981). In reference to Schäffner, Political Discourse Analysis (PDA) and Translation Studies can benefit from closer cooperation. (PDA) tries to define why a particular word, phrase or structure during the translation process has been chosen over another one, also analysing the ST with (PDA) to pinpoint emotive and persuasive aspect of the language used in the speeches is crucial to deliver a quality translation.

As Jones et al (1994:5) put it, “at the micro level we use a variety of techniques to get our own way: persuasion, rational argument, irrational strategies, threats, entreaties, bribes, manipulation – anything we think will work”. These micro level techniques mentioned above are actually kinds of linguistic action that is discourse; “politics involves reconciling differences through discussion and persuasion. Communication is therefore central to politics” (Hague et al. 1998:3-4). What is clear is that political activity does not exist without the use of language. The basis tenet is that we do not translate words or grammatical structures, but texts as communicative occurrences (cf. de Beaugrande & Dressler, 1981).

2.2.2 Translation and political discourse as communicative occurrences

“Translation is first of all communication, to be precise, interlingual and intercultural communication” (Trosborg 1997: 120). It is usually the case that the source text (ST) itself fulfils a particular function in the source language SL community, at a particular time, at a

particular place addressed to a more or less specific audience with knowledge about the subject of the text and probable text-typological conventions. “When the source text is translated, it will address a new audience in the new target language (TL) community at a different time and place” (Neubert 1985:71) the subject knowledge of the target text TT addressees may be more or less the same as that of the ST addressees. The function of the TT may be the same as the one of the ST or it may be different (Trosborg 1997: 120). This brief definition of translation applies to political speeches which is the main concern of this study.

Political discourse is frequently associated not only for the specific addressee of the text producer but may be of interest for a wider audience for instance in this case includes the English speaking world that may have an interest in Tunisia . Since politics is more and more internationalized, translation too, is becoming more and more important, especially in terms of quality where political analysts and foreign embassies needs to know the level of genuineness in the speeches of the president. Here it is detrimental that the translations reflect and transfer adequately the emotive and expressive aspects of the speeches. Political discourse lexicon is mainly devised according to criteria of emotiveness and persuasion to reach a given goal. Hence, the jargon used not only may be chosen because of official criteria, but also because they efficiently give emphasis to or de-emphasize political attitudes and opinions, move people, manipulate public opinion, manufacture political consent, or legitimate political power.

Newmark takes it as axiomatic that “politics pervades every aspect of human thought and activities”, which highlights “the trouble with the translation of political language that it is an abstraction (rather more than most translation) of an abstraction”. He adds that “politics is the most general and universal aspect and sphere of human activity and in its reflection in language it often appears in powerful terms or in impotent jargon” (Newmark 1991: 146).

These powerful terms and impotent jargon are usually instances of emotive language to persuade and move people .For instance the use of powerful terms such as:

وسيطبق القانون على هؤلاء بكل حزم

Law will be enforced rigorously against these people

and impotent jargon such as

ان البطالة شغل شاغل لسائر بلدان العالم المتقدمة منها والنامية ونحن في تونس نبدل
كل الجهود للحد منها ومعالجة

*Unemployment is a major concern in the different countries of
the world, be they developed or emerging; and we, in Tunisia,
are straining every nerve to curb it and deal with its effects and
impact”*

According to Newmark (1991: 146) the four facts about political concepts are that they are partly **cultural-bound**, mainly **value-laden**, **historically conditioned** and like all concepts, **abstractions** in spite of continuous efforts to concretize them, these political facts are actually used as a tool to move people and persuade them. The following is an exemplification of such political concepts:

Among the **Cultural bound instances** and concepts in the corpus studied is the use of the Tunisian dialect in the last speech to appeal to the population e.g.

واليوم نؤكد بيزي من اللجوء للكرطوش الحي ، الكرطوش موش مقبول ، ما عندوش
منبرر

*I say stop using live ammunition. Live ammunition is not
acceptable and is not justifiable*

Also some **value-laden concepts** detected in the data to raise fear for example “عمل إرهابي” =act of terrorism” in an attempt to give the demonstrations a cloak of terrorist act. Another instance of value-laden concept is the insinuated threat that those who incite destruction will face a heavy handed prosecution:

إننا نقول لكل من يعمد إلى النيل من مصالح البلاد أو يغرر بشبابنا وبأبنائنا وبناتنا في
المدارس والمعاهد ويدفع بهم إلى الشغب والفوضى نقول بكل وضوح أن القانون
سيكون هو الفيصل

*To all those who seek to undermine the country's interests or to
mislead our youth, sons and daughters in primary and
secondary schools and incite them to trouble-making and chaos,
.we clearly say: the law will have the final say*

Historically conditioned concepts are also found in the speeches for instance reminding the people with the appeal for re-electing the president for a new term after 2014 as well as bringing the image of his pledge that there will be no life-long governance:

ولذلك فاني أجدد الشكر لكل من ناشدني للترشح لسنة 2014 ، ولكني أرفض
المساس بشرط السن للترشح لرئاسة الجمهورية

*I wish to thank all who launched appeals so that I stand as
candidate for the 2014 presidential elections.*

Among the **abstractions** found in the speeches I may site the following as examples:

ونحن لا ندخر جهدا لتفادي مثل هذه الحالات بالمعالجة الخصوصية الملائمة
مواصلين سياساتنا وبرامجنا من أجل التشغيل ورعاية ضعاف الحال والإحاطة
بالأسر المعوزة وتفعيل التنمية الجهوية عبر برامج استثمارية متوالية شملت كل
مناطق البلاد

*Thus, we pursue our policies and programs of employment,
protection of the disadvantaged categories, care for poor
families and vitalization of regional development, through
successive investment programs covering all regions of the
country*

The underlined terms refer to general abstractions and political concepts that still remain general and elusive to the hearer of the text in an attempt to persuade and remind people that he is doing his best for the sake of poor people through his policies.

The previous review identifies political discourse and translation as communicative occurrences. Emotively loaded political speeches are used by politicians to achieve a specific political aim; the following part will focus on what makes a political discourse appealing and persuasive to achieve these political ends with an eye on translation.

2.3 Emotiveness and expressive expressions with an eye on translation

2.3.1 Theoretical background

The emotive meaning can be defined as a trend in the language directly related to feelings and the psychological attitude of the speaker when expressing something; this in turn may produce affective responses in people towards the matter addressed. Thus, while translating such aspect from Arabic into English, in both languages it arouses different psychological and emotional responses. Political discourse plays a considerable influence on the mind and behaviour of the members of a speech community (Al-Hamad and Al-Shunnag 2011-149).

To fully grasp the meaning of political discourse, it is mandatory to think of language as mediation, based on the tenet that politics cannot be conveyed and conducted without language. Newmark (1991: 146) claims that “Politics is the most general and universal aspect and sphere of human activity and in its reflection in language it often appears in powerful emotive terms”.

Using emotive expressions enhances Arabic political speech and gives it a kind of power. This emotive and manipulative force cannot be grasped easily by non-native speakers of Arabic therefore it needs research and synthesis before approaching any translational action. Hence, it becomes the translator’s duty to transfer the matching of emotive expressions to generate the identical effect and have the same impact on the target audience as they had on the source audience.

The translation of emotive expressions gives translators the dilemma of lexical incommensurateness. There are many problems facing the translator of political discourse with respect to emotiveness, specifically when using discourse analysis as a tool to achieve quality of the product. The analysis and translation of emotiveness in this study can be seen in the context of Trosborg’s model for discourse analysis and House’s model for TQA. Within this vain we may ask the following questions: how does a translator transfer such expressions with quality to give the intentional impact in the TT with minimal loss of meaning, so that a better comprehension between SL and TL could be maintained? To

what extent translation oriented ST-TT analysis help to detect and then transfer these emotive instances with quality?

2.3.2 Review of related literature to emotiveness in political discourse

Zheng (2000) defines 'political discourse' as: "A mixed product of personal development and the relevant social environment in which an individual grows". Emotive expressions are introduced in political speeches to incite the feelings of the addressees which may be used as a tool to win their consent and support to what is delivered. Shunnaq (1993: 37-38) points out that: Three types of lexical items pertaining to Arabic-English translation of emotiveness in political discourse can be identified: The first includes items of the source language (SL) which have straightforward equivalents in the target language (TL), the second includes items which have only partial equivalents, and the third includes items which do not have equivalents. Lucas (1992: 339) points out that "one way to generate emotional appeal is to use emotion-laden words". Within this sphere, President Ben Ali uses emotive expressions in his speeches as a manipulative and persuasive means of conveying his attitude towards urging political issues. Hence in his speeches he emotively manipulates his discourse to win his audience consent and support. As Wilson (1990: 18-19) states: "Certainly, politicians use words and sentences in an emotive manner; it is part of their aim to create a feeling of solidarity, to arouse emotions such as fear, hate or joy".

Barkho (1987: 147) remarks that "a general characteristic of Arabic political terminology is that it is charged with high emotive meaning, which renders it difficult to translate". Translation is considered as cross-language transfer of meaning. Translation is understood as the process by which a meaning in a given SL is semantically as well as linguistically transformed into a TL. Therefore translating emotiveness can give serious hurdles for a translator handling such discourse. The role of the translator is to discern how to restructure the emotive and persuasive meaning of the source language and how to convey it in the target language. For this reason, it is imperative that the translator possess discourse analysis knowledge as well as TQA models necessary to produce an equivalent translation with quality.

Nida (1964) defines connotative meaning as: “the aspects of author and the emotional response of a receptor. It can be bad or good, strong or weak”. Nida claims that the relationship between a source text and its translation involves ‘cognitive content’ and ‘emotive response’. He concludes that emotiveness is the result of the interaction of author, text, and audience. He goes on to state three principles of connotative meaning: the speaker associated with the word, the practical circumstances in which the word is used, and the linguistic characteristics of the word.

Shunnaq (1993) investigates different characteristics concerning lexical incongruence in Arabic–English translation due to emotiveness and persuasion in Arabic. He partitioned emotive expressions into three types: positive, negative, and neutral. He categorizes the main sources of emotive expressions into figures of speech, cultural expressions and naturally emotive expressions. He concludes that translating Arabic emotive expressions is not an easy task since it deals with the connotative meaning which is very difficult to transfer, as it involves expressions dealing with culturally bound emotive concepts.

Thus the study will focus on how language can be used as a source of cultural worth and creative power in Arabic as well as in English. The study should reveal how President Ben Ali uses language as a powerful tool in gaining political advantage. The speeches are studied from the various angles of discourse analysis and political rhetoric techniques to determine the needed strategies to achieve a quality translation. In the following chapter the study will use these various angles of discourse analysis to pinpoint the emotive structures as well as the manipulative aspects found in the speeches of Ben Ali, this will serve as a springboard for the translator to seek a quality translation product.

As shown in the previous review, emotiveness poses a great challenge to translators of Arabic political speeches; however these hurdles and difficulties can be bypassed through prior translation oriented text analysis as well as knowledge of translation quality assessment models.

2.4 Translation Quality Assessment: Review of merits and defects.

2.4.1 Pre-linguistic studies

Within the field of TQA research, philologists, theorists, poets and professional translators described and characterized the first steps of translation quality assessment and translation criticism. However, for them they regarded translation quality assessment from a subjective and anecdotal viewpoint. For instance, they would characterize a given translation by stating that such a translation is faithful to the original, or reflects original's flavour. Such approach was criticised because it gives a vague and subjective statements of quality. Among the prominent scholars who advocated such approach, we may site Savory who merely tried to link the quality of a target text to the personalities of the translator, the author and the audience. This is reiterated in his saying that "the most satisfying translations are made by those whose personalities are in tune with those of writers and also with those of the readers "(Savory 1957: 50-54).

Other qualitative vague statements postulate that a good translation is one which is not identified as a translation ; as asserted by Elsen 1963 "une traduction de qualité est une traduction dont la forme fait oublier au lecteur qu'il s'agit précisément d'une traduction" . In addition, we may cite Newmark's statement that "a good translation fulfils its intent" (Peter Newmark, 1988: 192). Since the study focuses on emotiveness and manipulation and the way the translator dealt with them, the quality in the translation rests on translator's precise understanding of these concepts in the texts that the original writer wants to convey.

2.4.2 Response-based psycholinguistic studies:

Among the major scholars that advocated such approach, we may cite Forster who claims that "a good translation is one which fulfils the same purpose in the new language as the original did" Leonard Forster (1958: 6). Zilahy 1963 shares with him the same approach stressing that a translation is considered good when it arouses in us the same effect as did the original" (Zilahy, 1963:285). The current study is in line with Zilhay's approach to TQA since it will focus on the emotive aspect in political speeches as a case study, to

detect how the translator will overcome the challenges he faces while transferring the expressive side of the speeches. However, the above mentioned claims and assertions have not progressed beyond the pronouncement of broad non-verified principles. Within the same vein Nida (1964-182) suggested three criteria for judging a translation summarized as follows:

- **General efficiency of the communication process:** *maximal reception for the minimal effort of decoding.*
- **Comprehension of intent:** *explained through accuracy where the meaning of the source language message is represented in the translation judged in terms of its comprehensibility in receptor culture.*
- **Equivalence of response:** *summarized through his famous approach of dynamic equivalence of translation.*

Pondering upon these criteria, we have to assert that it is undeniably true that a translation should produce an equivalent response with focus on the emotiveness of the speech and its expressive aspect; the question is whether the degree to which this requirement is met can be empirically tested?

Newmark rightly maintains that the equivalent response principle especially is mentalistic and needs further definition; however, the crucial question is whether the response can be measured. To answer this question a number of scholars attempted to develop and make use of certain experimental studies in order to empirically measure these responses.

These experimental studies tried to operationalize the response-based criteria for translation quality assessment. For instance, Nida and Taber tried to test the translation through the cloze technique which refers to the degree of comprehensibility of a text in relation to the degree of predictability. The second test suggested by Nida and Taber is the elicitation of respondents' reactions to several translation alternatives. The third test is to read aloud the TT to some respondents who will be asked to explain the content to several other individuals who were not present at the first reading, the test aims to find out how well the meaning comes across in terms of total content correctness of understanding. The fourth test is reading aloud the TT by several individuals before an audience, in the reading

aloud any places in the text at which the readers clearly have difficulty in reading will indicate problems of translation.

Such experimental studies seem to offer empirically solid tests for assessing a given translation, but they are criticized due to certain limitations. For instance the adopted tests for assessing quality assessment shows limited goal of establishing ease of comprehension and degree of intelligibility , unless these tests can be strictly defined through linguistic means . In addition, these tests lack reference to the ST and focus mainly on the way TT affects its intended readership. Therefore, it is imperative to develop an objective method of determining the particular semantic, stylistic, functional and pragmatic qualities of the source text and then try to determine whether and to what extent the translation matches these characteristics. Hence, came the need for establishing reliable translation-oriented ST-TT analysis to be used as a yardstick for translation criticism and translation quality assessment.

2.4.3 Source text-based studies:

Advocates of this approach claim that the norm of usage should be taken as a yardstick in the objectification of translation criticism. Levy 1967 asserts, “Like any linguistic activity translation is a creative process which leaves the translator the freedom of choice between several approximately equivalent possibilities of realizing situational meaning” (cf. Levy, 1967:1171). Based on such approach Koller 1974 proposed a model for translation quality assessment summarized as follows:

1. ST criticism with a view to transferability into TT
2. Translation comparison in which the particular methods of translation used in the production of a given translation text are described
3. Evaluation of the translation not in vague general criteria but according to adequate or not adequate according to the text specific features derived in (1.) and then measured against the native speaker’s faculty for meta-linguistic judgments.

Likewise, Reiss tried to make the ST a starting point for her analysis, which will pave the way for her translation quality assessment. She claims that it is necessary to determine the

function and textual type of the source text while evaluating a given translation. For her the main criteria for a good translation is to keep text type equivalent in an adequate translation, however such claim is criticized by House as a programmatic one and gives no indication as to the precise method of establishing textual function and textual type.

House insists that translation is a 'linguistic textual phenomenon and can be legitimately described, analysed and assessed as such' (House 1997:118–19), but clearly distinguishes her model of quality assessment from purely text based approaches such as those of Reiß's (1971) and Koller's (1979/2004), where pairs of source and target texts are compared with a view to discovering syntactic, semantic, stylistic and pragmatic regularities of transfer. The model proposed by House (1977/1981, 1997), based on pragmatic theories of language use, claims that quality in translation is achieved when the translation has a function which is equivalent to that of the original, and employs equivalent pragmatic means for achieving that function (Baker, 2008 :150).

Jeremy Munday (2001:93) gives a brief outline of House's model as follows:

1. A profile is produced of the ST register.
2. To this is added a description of the ST genre realized by the register
3. Together, this allows a 'statement of function' to be made for the ST, including the ideational and interpersonal component of that function (in other words, what information is being conveyed and what the relationship is between sender and receiver).
4. The same descriptive process is then carried out for the TT.
5. The TT profile is compared to the ST profile and a statement of 'mismatches' or errors is produced, categorized according to genre and to the situational dimensions of register and genre; these dimensional errors are referred to as 'covertly erroneous errors', to distinguish them from 'overtly erroneous errors', which are denotative mismatches or target system errors.
6. A 'statement of quality' is then made of the translation.
7. Finally, the translation can be categorized into one of two types: overt translation or covert translation.

As far as House's model is concerned, Gutt (1991: 46-9) raises the question as to whether it is possible to recover authorial intention and ST function from register analysis. Even if it

is possible, the basis of House's model is to discover 'mismatches' between ST and TT. Yet, while mismatches may indicate translation errors, they may also be caused by other translation strategies such as explicitation or compensation.

The following study strives to assess how political discourse is translated with focus on the emotive and expressive aspect of the speeches, how and to what extent the translator managed to transfer the expressive side of the speeches? How can he use register and genre as a spring board to reach a quality translation? Therefore reviewing translation quality assessment is crucial to this study, since the dissertation is concerned with the analysis of emotive language ;the response based psycholinguistic approach as well as source text-based approach are detrimental to the study. The present dissertation shall adopt House's model for analysis as it is a source text –based study, the model will be used as a tool as well as an end to analyse translation of emotive language in political speeches (see chapter 3 data analysis).

2.5 Translation oriented ST-TT analysis as a tool for quality assessment

2.5.1 What is discourse analysis?

So abundant are definitions of discourse that many linguistics books on the subject now open with a survey of definitions. In their classic papers in discourse analysis for example Jaworski and Coupland (1991:1-3) include ten definitions from a wide range of sources. They all however fall into three main categories: (1) anything beyond the sentences (2) language use (3) a broader range of social practice that includes non-linguistic and non-specific instances of language(Deborah Schiffrin, Deborah Tannen, Heidi Ehernberger Hamilton 2003:1).

2.5.2 Scope of cooperation

Dealing with translation from the vintage point of source text analysis has a very long tradition both in the discipline of translation studies as well as translation quality assessment. This is primarily valid because there is a broad consensus that understanding a text is a perquisite for translating it hence assessing its accuracy and adequacy.

Understanding a given source text involves reflecting on linguistic structures, rhetoric, pragmatics which a text or a speech displays, taking into consideration that these discorsal strategies where chosen by the text producer are to be seen as the most appropriate to fulfil

the intended persuasion and emotiveness which the speaker wanted to achieve with the speech for specific communicative situation in a specific sociocultural context for specific addressees. In analysing texts as products of discursive actions, PDA researchers use either original texts or translations. In the latter case, full attention needs to be given to the nature of those texts, i.e. they need to be taken as what they are: translations, i.e. target texts operating in a new socio-cultural context and based on a source text which functioned in its original socio-cultural context.

The following review reflects on a general agreement that source text analysis of emotive expressions in a given political speech is indispensable phase in the translation process, hence, can be considered as a tool as well as an end for translation quality assessment. The aim of discourse analysis for translation is to identify specific textual features which are relevant for the process of translation; such analysis has to be translation-oriented analysis. For instance assessing the translation of a political speech can be analyzed from a comparative perspective to appraise it and find out what are the strategies and methods adopted for such a particular genre. Source text analysis as a phase in the translation process has its own specific purpose: “to identify and highlight specific cultural features which might be expected to present translation problems in order to steer translation decisions” (Erdmann et al.1994:4).

With some of its roots in linguistics, translation studies have always used concepts and methods of linguistics, text linguistics, pragmatics, and discourse analysis in its own disciplinary discourse (Schaffner2002:1). However, translation quality assessment has not made use of Discourse Analysis, Critical Discourse Analysis, and Political Discourse Analysis concepts to a similar extent, although analyses were conducted on the basis of systemic functional grammar. The analysis of the specific conditions of the production and assessment of the translated version, thus, needs to be an integral part of the “toolkit” of discourse analysis as well as translation quality assessment. These approaches link linguistic forms to social, and hence also to political activity. A political discourse perspective to translation can shed new light to understanding quality assessment of political speeches. In the data analysis part of this paper, the dissertation adopts TQA (House) and PDA (Trosborg) concepts and approaches that could be useful to assess emotiveness and persuasion in political speeches, thus also indicating scope for cooperation between these disciplines.

The aim of the approach is to achieve an in-depth understanding of the source text (ST) through detailed analysis of genre and register. Understanding the text in full gives the translator a thorough overview and the possibility of maintaining or adapting the ST in a conscious way to meet the demands of the target text TT Skopos. It must also be noted that the approach emphasises not only the quality of the product (the translation) but also how the process is administered. Thus we are dealing with a process-oriented approach to translation (Schäffner. 2002:9)

A translation-oriented ST-TT analysis coupled with TQA models on the basis of the model proposed by Trosborg, and on the basis of Houses model for TQA these two models combined intend to heighten evaluators' awareness of the process involved in translating and in the assessment of a given translation. It will help both translators and evaluators reflect on what are they doing, and it will also provide them with arguments and terms to use when commenting on the translation decisions. They can be considered tools for developing translation criticism.

2.5.3 Textual analysis and translation: Schäffner's overview of Trosborg's model

Translation-oriented text analysis of ST-TT is a preliminary step to detect the emotive aspect of the speeches that will serve later on as a tool to reach a quality translation. In order to reach a quality translation of a political speech we are bound to follow certain procedures and strategies .The aim of the study is to assess how political discourse is translated with focus on the emotive and expressive aspect of the speeches, how and to what extent the translator managed to transfer the expressive side of the speeches? How can he use political discourse analysis as a spring board to reach a quality translation?

Hence, it is imperative for the translator before proceeding in translation to come up with a ST profile that will cover the situational aspects of the speeches dealing with the place of communication, time of communication and the purpose of the communication. Then he will move to determine the field that is to say the domain and subject matter of the speech ,this will be followed up with pinpointing tenor i.e. sender receiver relationship such analysis will lead to the determination of genre .Since we are concerned in this study with the emotive and expressive language used and the way it is translated it is crucial also to determine the ideational and experiential features of language used in the speeches

(realization of field –language as meaning) a description of semantic aspects of the discourse used including collocations metaphors images ,parallel structures etc. The translator should move to scrutinize the interpersonal features of language used (realization of tenor-language as communication) here the translator should focus on the communicative functions and the speech acts used in the speeches to weigh the emotive appeal that these speech acts carry (e.g. Expressive, verdictives, directives and declarations) this will lead us to weigh the response elicited by the these speech acts. Finally the translator will move to give an overview of the textual features of language (realisation of mode – language as text) with focus on Text type (narration, description, exposition, argumentation, instruction),this will be followed by a conclusion of translation strategies that shall be implemented as well as some translation comments (Schäffner: 2002 :51-52).

2.6 Summary

Political discourse, emotive language and translation are influenced by each other. As far as the translation process is concerned, translation quality assessment models as well as political discourse analysis are essential in determining the outcome of the translation process. Translating emotiveness within political speeches presents serious hurdles for the translators; where they need to overcome these challenges that face them in translating political discourse especially when it comes to expressive language and its connotations. While translating political texts and political discourse focusing on the emotive aspect and manipulative character of language, the broader translational procedures and ST-TT framework in which such process is embedded has to be taken into consideration.

Hence the previous literature review was mandatory before embarking on any data analysis, this chapter tried to cover the main tools and models necessary for quality translation of political speeches with focus on emotive language. The next chapter will embark on data analysis using the above mentioned model of translation quality assessment proposed by House and translation oriented source text analysis model proposed by Trosborg, to highlight and appraise the way emotive expression in the political speeches of Ben Ali are translated.

Chapter three: Data analysis

3.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with data analysis that focuses on the translation of emotiveness and persuasion in the political speeches of Ben Ali during the Tunisian revolution. The analysis will be based on translation-oriented ST as well as TT analysis with application of House's model of translation quality assessment as elaborated in the previous chapter (2.4.3 Source text-based studies). The corpus consists of written translations of the delivered speeches of President Ben Ali. Within the same vein of the design of the theoretical framework adopted in the previous chapter, the translation of the speeches will be analyzed in this chapter from three main vantage points: Translation oriented ST - TT analysis, translation quality assessment and rendition of emotiveness into English. The analysis will examine various aspects of the speeches, one aspect of this is the emotiveness. The rendition of emotiveness is the most important aspect I'm focusing on. The boundaries between these three angles of research, are blurred and intertwined, and, in practice, they interchange with each other.

3.2 Methodology and Data Collection

The corpus of the dissertation consists of written manuscripts of Arabic speeches delivered by President Ben Ali along with their English translations. These speeches were delivered during the Tunisian revolution (17/12/2010 until 14/01/2011). In this period, Tunisia witnessed an uprising against Ben Ali and his regime. These speeches were delivered by the then incumbent president to his enraged population revolting against his policies and his inner circle, asking for reform and accountability. All of the three speeches were delivered in the capital Tunis. The President's main concern in his speeches is to appeal and persuade the Tunisian people through the use of emotive language. The researcher has collected Ben Ali's speeches and their translations from the website of the Tunisian News Agency Tap, (www.tap.info.tn/en/), which is the official state news agency of Tunisia.

The thesis uses a corpus of various speeches as data collected mostly through websites of news networks and embassies. The corpus texts include: Three political speeches delivered by the ousted Tunisian president during the Tunisian revolution also known as the

revolution of dignity and freedom; three Arabic transcripts of the speeches were translated into English and published on the website of the Tunisian News Agency Tap:

خطاب قرطاج 28 ديسمبر

Carthage speech 28 December 2010(TAP) First speech

خطاب قرطاج 10 جانفي

Carthage speech 10 January 2010(TAP) Second speech

خطاب قرطاج 13 جانفي 2011

Carthage speech 13 January 2010(TAP) Third speech

A copy of the original text and its translations is attached at the very end of the paper.

The speeches were selected in order to assess how the translator managed to transfer emotiveness and persuasion in the speeches to a different target audience with quality. Adding to that these speeches have not been investigated yet. Furthermore these speeches continue to receive a great deal of attention due to the fact that Tunisians managed to spark what is known as the Arab spring or Arab uprising. To fulfill the purpose of the dissertation, the researcher analyzed and identified quality translation of emotive expressions using House's model for TQA and Trosborg's model of translation-oriented ST-TT analysis (refer to 2.5.3 Textual analysis and translation).

The researcher believes that to achieve a quality translation of the emotive aspect within political speeches, it is crucial for the translator to proceed with a translation-oriented textual analysis that will serve as a tool as well as an end for assessing the translation of political speeches, in doing so the translator can pinpoint the strong emotive and persuasive aspect of language used, hence the way these political speeches are translated.

The data analysis then subjects the translations to House's ST-TT analysis model to see whether the emotive meaning in the source language (SL) that the study would come up with is preserved in the English translation or not. Then the study will try to identify the procedures and strategies used by the translator to preserve the emotive aspect of the original speeches in the target language with quality. Understanding the way emotive language functions in the ST as well as in the TT should be analyzed by the translator to identify the instances of persuasion and the evoking of feelings within the addressee. Such

analysis is crucial for the translator of emotive political speeches to produce a quality translation.

3.3 Translation-oriented ST and TT analysis

3.3.1 Situational features:

The place of communication of the speeches is Tunisia; the time of communication is during the Tunisian revolution (17/12/2010-14/01/2011), during times of turmoil and political upheaval. The two first speeches are written to be delivered exclusively in unmarked MSA (Modern Standard Arabic); however, the last speech is marked with the use of Tunisian dialect. The shift in language between the two first speeches and the last one reveals a strategy to appeal as well as to move Tunisians to believe in their president. Yet the change in register used as well as the tone employed between the speeches is not reflected in the translation for these delivered speeches. If we take into consideration the variable of readership and mode of communication change we will constitute that there is a translation loss in terms of emotiveness and persuasion since the English reader is subjected to three speeches that are translated into Standard English.

In terms of social class the two first speeches are unmarked, as no social dialect is found; these two speeches are intended for the political elite targeting Tunisian social fabric that includes the educated and the middle class in general . The occurrences of terms such as:

مجلس وزاري - تحقيق مآرب سياسوية - تكريس الحوار مبدأ وأسلوباً - تألمنا لسقوط
ضحايا ...

*Cabinet meeting- petty political targets- to entrench dialogue as
principle and method of communication - We were saddened for the
victims*

These examples show that the speaker is trying to appeal to the educated Tunisian. This classification of targeted audience goes well with the readers of TAP which is thought to cover an educated middle class readership with interest in politics and social development.

The purpose of the communication of these speeches is to move, persuade people and to evoke in them different emotions ranging from sympathy and fear to nationalism .These evoked emotions by the delivered speeches are supposed to converge in order to make

Tunisians believe in the sincerity and genuineness of the appeals, threats and promises voiced in the speeches. In order to say that the TT is accurate and faithful to the source text these emotions should be experienced by the TT audience (equivalent effect –equivalent response) (see 2.4.2 Response-based psycholinguistic studies).

3.3.2 Register: Field /Tenor/Mode

Although, Halliday's grammar is extremely complex, and that is why, the present study has chosen to select and simplify those elements which are of particular relevance for translation analysis and assessment. For Juliane House, the central concept is register analysis to draft ST and TT profiles for later comparison. The situational differences between texts may be accounted for by the three aspects of context, i.e. field, tenor and mode. For Halliday and Hasan(1990:20), these aspects collectively define the context of situation of a text i.e. Register.

3.3.2.1 Field analysis:

Field: language as form and meaning: what is being written about: A call for calm and renouncement of violence. Field refers to the total event in which the text is functioning, together with the purposive activity of the speaker or writer, thus including the subject matter as one element in it (Schäffner 2002:11). The field of a text is associated with **ideational component**, which is realized through transitivity patterns (verb types, active passive structures, participants in the process, stylistic devices etc.).

Pondering upon the corpus we notice that the translator used a number of emotion verbs such as:

وتألمنا لما حدث شديد الالم/ حزني والمي كبيران/ ونواسيهم صادقين الحب

*We **felt** deep pain / my sadness and my pain **are great** / we **express** to them our **sincere sympathy***

These verbs are translated here to reflect the emotive aspect of the source speeches.

In terms of active and passive structures that realizes the ideational component, the translated text shows that the active voice dominates the speeches, the use of the active

voice is so abundant because it is simpler and direct, easily grasped by the recipients of the speech, hence the audience can easily identify with the subject who is doing the action. The use of active voice can be considered as a means of persuasion and raising emotions within the targeted audience. The translated speeches also reflect the use of active voice as given in the source speeches to maintain same response (refer to 2.4.2 Response-based psycholinguistic studies).

Recognizing transitivity patterns in the speeches is the first important step to being able to decode the emotive and persuasive hidden meanings in the speeches; this preliminary analysis should be used to achieve a quality translation. The ideational metafunction engenders resources for construing our experience of the world around us and inside us; the ideational system at clause rank is transitivity (Halliday 1997). Transitivity in the speeches is concerned with construing one particular domain of the audience experience which is influencing people and moving them to renounce demonstrating e.g.:

Those ill-wishers (participants involved) exploited (material process) the issue of unemployment (means and instrument), by manipulating (material process) an isolated (attribute) case of despair (goal)

لقد ركب هؤلاء المغالطون موضوع البطالة بتوظيف حالة يأس فردية

Both ST as well as TT display a vast majority use of material process as well as verbal process , these processes are used to denote and describe actions that aims to persuade people and raise in them certain feelings such as fear , joy and nationalism .These verbal processes add to the dynamics of the text: they make the text seem more dynamic by referring to the sequence of events in a value-laden manner using words and expressions which may be characterized in the last speech as colloquial language .Here the translator has shown a great deal of accuracy while transmitting these emotions in the TT language :

E.g.

وأسفى كبير، كبير جدا ، وعميق جدا ، وعميق جدا ، فكفى عنفا كفى عنفا وعطيت التعليمات كذلك لوزير الداخلية، وكررت ،واليوم تؤكد بزي من اللجوء للكرطوش الحي ، الكرطوش موش مقبول ،ما عندوش مبرر الا لا قدر الله حد يحاول يفك سلاحك ويهجم عليك بالنار وغيرها ،ويجبرك على الدفاع عن النفس.

My sadness is great, very deep and great, very profound. So, I say clearly enough to violence! Enough to violence! I have also instructed the Interior Minister and I reiterate this. I say stop using live ammunition. Live ammunition is not acceptable and is not justifiable, except, God protects us, if any one seeks to snatch your weapon or attacks you with a fire arm, or compels you to defend yourself.

we notice that by including expressive illustrations , the last speech succeeds in providing the reader of the translated speech with direct and immediately comprehensible links to the actual contents of the speeches , also we notice the overabundant use of intensifiers and modifiers that amplifies the meaning of the already value laden words such as :sadness and violence. Hence it becomes clear to the reader of the TT that the Tunisian president is trying to evoke in his people certain pre-calculated feelings that are supposed to converge in order to manipulate people to stop demonstrating.

Lexical frames and chains create coherence throughout the text and emphasize the emotive aspect of the speeches, through the use of certain words these words fall into three major categories: **listing of facts**, **threats** and **appeals** which combine into an overall pattern and function as the skeleton of the speech, such skeleton should be respected in the translation, here are some examples for illustration:

Listing of facts:

*على إثر ما شهدته بعض المدن والقرى بعدد من الجهات الداخلية من أحداث شغب وتشويش
وأضرار بالأماكن العمومية والخاصة أحداث عنيفة دامية أحيانا أدت إلى وفاة مدنيين
وإصابة عدد من رجال الأمن*

*Following the troubles and acts of vandalism that took place in some
villages and cities in a number of interior regions, causing damage to
public and private properties.*

*وسيستوعب هذا المجهود أيضا كل حاملي الشهادات العليا الذين تجاوزت مدة بطالتهم عامين
قبل موفى سنة 2012 /نعم قبل موفى 2012 وأتعهد بذلك*

This effort will cover all university graduates who have remained unemployed for more than two years before the end of 2012 --Yes, before the end of 2012, and I commit myself to it.

Threats:

كما أن لجوء أقلية من المتطرفين والمحرضين المأجورين ضد مصالح بلادهم الى العنف والشغب في الشارع وسيلة للتعبير أمر مرفوض في دولة القانون مهما كانت أشكاله وهو مظهر سلبي وغير حضارى يعطي صورة مشوهة عن بلادنا تعوق اقبال المستثمرين والسواح بما ينعكس على احداثات الشغل التي نحن في حاجة اليها للحد من البطالة. وسيطبق القانون على هؤلاء بكل حزم.

It is not acceptable that a minority of extremists and agitators in the pay of others, and against the country's interests, resort to violence and street disturbances as means of expression, whatever their form is in a State of law like ours. This is a negative and anti-civil behavior that presents a distorted image of our country and impedes the flow of investors and tourists which impacts negatively on job creation, while we need them to curb joblessness. Law will be enforced rigorously against these people.

Appeals:

We rely on the co-operation of all

ونعول على تعاون الجميع

We call on parents and all citizens to protect their children from those agitators and trouble-makers,

واننا ندعو الأولياء وسائر المواطنين إلى الحفاظ على أبنائهم من هؤلاء المشاغبيين والمفسدين بتكثيف الإحاطة بهم وتوعيتهم بمخاطر توظيفهم واستغلالهم من قبل هذه المجموعات المتطرفة

For preserving Tunisia's glory and invulnerability is a sacred mission entrusted to all Tunisian men and women.

بل يجب أن تستخلص جميع الأطراف العبرة منها وان نواصل مسيرتنا بكل ارادة وحماس
لان عزة تونس ومناعتها امانة مقدسة لدى التونسيين والتونسيات جميعا

A very striking feature of the speeches especially in the last one is the use of expressive metaphors. The president makes use of metaphors/images to make the speeches more direct and easily grasped by the targeted audience e.g.

التونسي المتحضر ، التونسي المتسامح

We, the civilized and tolerant Tunisians.

By choosing these images which have a clear connotative link to the image of the peaceful ordinary Tunisian, the president deliberately pursues the emotion of forgiveness and logic in attempt to persuade the agitated demonstrators to relinquish protests. However in terms of translation the translator sought to avoid the use of repetition as used in the ST and used the inclusive ‘We’ instead ,which actually mirrors the emotiveness of the repetition used in the ST and brings the same feeling to target reader .

Emotiveness manifests itself also in the abundant use of repetition. “A common form of repetition in Arabic is the repetition of the same word or even of a whole phrase in particular” (cf.Dickins and Watson 1999: 510-14) Repetition is the deliberate use of catch phrases more than once in a sentence or in the speeches as a whole to create a sense of emphasis in certain elements in the heart and mind of the ST listener or TT reader. For example the repetition of catch phrases such as:

وأنا فهمتكم أي نعم أنا فهمتكم

I have understood you, I have understood you all.

فهمتكم و فهمتكم الكل

I understood you, I understood you well.

وقلتكم أنا فهمتكم

I told you that I have understood your message

From translation quality assessment perspective these instances of lexical items and phrase repetition functions not only as a stylistic feature transmitted by the translator into the TT

,but also as a text building device contributing to the cohesion of the text hence to the acceptability and intelligibility of the TT by the targeted readership.

The repetitive use of these catch phrases appears to be a speech-writer's deliberate invocation of French leader Charles de Gaulle's famous "je vous ai compris" to French Algerians in 1958 during the Algerian war of independence. Hence, the catch phrase "I have understood you" can also be analyzed in terms of intertextuality. For instance, during the reading process our stored knowledge, experience and previous readings all affect the present reading/hearing perception. That is why the production and the reception of a given text/speech depend on the participants' knowledge of other texts/speeches. In his last speech, Ben Ali borrowed General de Gaulle phrase delivered in his speech in Algiers 1958 "Je vous ai compris! I have understood you" in order to give momentum to his speech within the intellectual sphere as well as appeal directly to the population declaring straightforward that he understood the Tunisians.

President Ben Ali also used Flashback as a tool to remind Tunisians of his achievement during his career. The flash back stylistic device is used in the speeches to raise emotions, give background and evoke nostalgia, to emphasise that president Ben Ali is the man of the situation as he always was. Examples for illustration:

لاني مضيت أكثر من 50 سنة من عمري في خدمة تونس في مختلف المواقع من الجيش الوطني الى المسؤوليات المختلفة و23 سنة على رأس الدولة ، كل يوم من حياتي كان ومازال لخدمة البلاد ، وقدمت التضحيات - وما نحش نعددها - بكلكم تعرفوها - ولم أقبل يوماً / وما نقبلش / باش تسيل قطرة دم واحدة من دماء التونسيين.

I have spent more than fifty years of my life in the service of Tunisia in different positions: from the National Army to the different decision-making positions and 23 years at the presidency. Each day of my life was and will always be in the service of the country; and I have made countless sacrifices. I have never accepted the bloodshed of Tunisians.

أني تعهدت يوم السابع من نوفمبر بأن لا رئاسة مدى الحياة لا رئاسة مدى الحياة ،ولذلك فاني أجدد الشكر لكل من ناشدني للترشح لسنة 2014 ، ولكني أرفض المساس بشرط السن للترشح لرئاسة الجمهورية.

I pledged on November 7, 1987 that there would be no lifetime presidency, no lifetime presidency. Once again, I wish to thank all who launched appeals so that I stand as candidate for the 2014 presidential elections

3.3.3.2Field: Translation Strategies for the ideational function

With regard to the ideational function, Emotiveness, transitivity and stylistic devices used are preserved in the target text (including lexical frames and chains). For example; repetition of catch phrases in the ST is preserved in the TT (see 3.3.2.1Field analysis). However preserving the meaning of a metaphorical image in the ST presented a challenge to the translator as he failed in one instance to fully convey the same image to the TT readership:

وعطيت التعليمات كذلك لوزير الداخلية، وكررت، واليوم نؤكد يزي من اللجوء
للكرطوش الحي، الكرطوش موش مقبول، ما عندوش مبرر إلا لا قدر الله حد يحاول
يفك سلاحك ويهجم عليك بالنار وغيرها، ويجبرك على الدفاع عن النفس

*I have also instructed the Interior Minister and I reiterate this. I say stop using live_ammunition. Live_ammunition is not acceptable and is not justifiable, except, **God protects us**, if any one seeks to snatch your weapon or attacks you with a fire arm, or compels you to defend yourself.*

Although the translator showed awareness of special culturally loaded terminology and sufficient knowledge of specialized content throughout the translation, He failed in this instance to convey the emotive meaning in this case: (إلا لا قدر الله = God protects us) There have been some changes in meaning, alteration that cannot be justified by the translation aim; hence will give faulty impression to the TT readership. Translation shows some misunderstanding of original. The translation here fails to carry the meaning and content where it should be translated as (God forbids instead of god protect us.) Hence some adjustments in this idiomatic expression must be carried out to fulfil the emotive aim of the ST.

3.3.2.3 Tenor analysis:

Tenor (language as communication, who is communicating and to whom: incumbent Tunisian president addressing his revolting population). Tenor refers to the type of role interactions, the set of social relations, permanent and temporary, among the participants involved. In the case of the speeches we are dealing with an asymmetrical relationship where we have one party represented by the head of state and the other side there is his interlocutor i.e. his population. The tenor of a text is associated with **interpersonal component**, which is realized through the patterns of modality (modal verbs and adverbs, and any evaluative lexis).

The examined speeches can be classified as authoritative statements, since the nature of these speeches derive their authority from the high status of the speaker (Head of State). These speeches have the personal stamp of their speaker, these speeches showcases denotative meaning and not connotative ones. For example, the personal stamp of the president manifests itself in the opening line of each speech. In the last speech ousted president Ben Ali opened his speech with these words “أيها الشعب التونسي”, such an opening sentence is very telling in the Tunisian context ; this was the first and last time where the president addresses his population referring to them as “dear fellow citizens” . He used to initiate his speeches with the famous opening words “أيها المواطنين أيتها المواطنين” . Both statements are superficially similar opening sentences that may have the same denotation namely ‘Tunisians as a population ‘ but they got different semantic and pragmatic uses . Tunisians grew with a rigid cold opening, where almost in every speech the president uses “أيها المواطنين أيتها المواطنين” as the opening sentence to address Tunisians, for Tunisians such opening refers directly to the feared president of the country , the opening refers and denotes authority and power of the executive branch. In his last speech Ben Ali knew that his population is now in stern anger with his policies and corruption , and he knew that he had to change the opening of his speech to mark a change in his policies and the way he is going to address his population .

However, the translation of the opening line does not carry the same impact experienced by the ST addresses, (Dear fellow citizens = أيها الشعب التونسي) (أيها المواطنين أيتها المواطنين = Fellow citizens) the translator sought to add the word “ Dear” to compensate the change in the opening line , this translation does not carry the emotive aspect of the change .Even the

translation of (أيها المواطنين أيتها المواطنات = Fellow citizens) doesn't carry the intended meaning hence the desired response in the TT reader. The literal translation of the opening line should be : “Dear men and women of Tunisia”; however in the official translation the translator did not manage to reflect the specificity of male and female citizens as Tunisia always fought for women rights and liberation ,that's why president Ben Ali always initiated his speeches with the opening line : أيها المواطنين أيتها المواطنات .

The vocative focus of language is the readership, the addressee. Here the term vocative refers to the sense of ‘calling upon’ the readership to act, think or feel, i.e. to react in the way intended by the speeches, Ben Ali uses the vocative function of language for addressing his rebellious people in some influenced languages. “This function of language has been given many other names, including ‘Conative,(denoting effort),instrumental, operative and pragmatic (in the sense of used to produce a certain effect on the readership” (Peter Newmark .1987:41).The speeches are actually written in a language that is immediately comprehensible to the readership ,for instance president Ben Ali initiates his final speech explaining clearly that he is going to speak with the language of all Tunisians ,thus for translation , the linguistic and cultural level of the SL speeches has to be reviewed before it is given a pragmatic impact. Few texts are purely expressive, informative or vocative: hence the concerned speeches can be considered as hybrid speeches that include all three functions, with emphasis on the expressive and vocative side.

The deliverer of the speeches would like to give the impression that he is describing a factual state of affairs where he uses an appealing style by giving recurrent promises with listings of facts. However, when examining the speeches closely, it is obvious that the dominant communicative function used in the speeches is the expressive function .The focus of attention is on the addressees, and the choice of words is subjective and personal. The reason why the president adopted such terminology is solely because he is trying to force a certain attitude onto the reader. The translation of the speeches actually can reveal to the English reader the writer's attitude mainly through the choice of lexis. A negative attitude towards the demonstrators is conveyed by many adjectives and adverbials as highlighted by the following examples:

Acts of vandalism;

أحداث شغب وتشويش

These violent, sometimes bloody events;

أحداث عنيفة دامية أحيانا

Hooded gangs;

عصابات ملثمة

Act of terrorism

عمل إرهابي

Erroneous slogans of despair and concocting false news

شعارات اليأس الكاذبة واقتعال الأخبار الزائفة

Since we are dealing with emotive analysis with an eye on translation quality, it is mandatory to focus on the epistemic and deontic modality .The speeches showcase instances of both epistemic and deontic modality. Epistemic modality is the speaker's assessment of probability and predictability. "It is external to the content, being a part of the attitude taken up by the speaker: his attitude, in this case, towards his own speech role as 'declarer'" (Halliday, 1970:349). The epistemic modality is used to express the way the speaker communicates his doubts, certainties, and guesses; his "modes of knowing".

Hence the realisation of epistemic modality can be used to gauge the degree of influence of the speeches on the addressees; therefore measure the degree of emotive response raised in the addressees, hence assessing the success of the translation. In these speeches there are a number of modals expressing certainty e.g. the occurrence of 'must', 'should', 'have to', 'has to' are used by the translator to convey that the speaker is fully committed to the truth value of his statements .Thus the use of epistemic modality in the TT functions as a

tool to persuade the reader, and makes what would otherwise have been representative appear as instructive and emotionally moving. Examples for illustration:

- لازموا - راني باش نعمل على - بل يجب أن - لا بد أن

Requires - I will work to promote - should - should

Also deontic modality is heavily used in the speeches where we find several instances of imperatives and directives; the mood is exclusively imperative. This indicates lack of probability and doubts, as could be expected, the speaker is trying to influence the reader to do something (relinquish protest), and want the reader to adopt his opinion and promises. The use of the imperative mood is closely linked to the instances of complex participation reflected by the speeches: the use of the second person pronoun *you* in the speeches indicate that the sender seeks to elicit some kind of response from the reader. Thus by including direct references to the addresses involved and directly appealing to the reader's personal participation; the president succeeds in adding even more elements to the textual dynamics of expressiveness.

When considering the level of formality, we are bound to pay attention to the structure of the speeches, the choice of lexis, the grammatical complexity as well as the degree of interaction with the addresses while translating a given speech. In general the two first speeches bear the marks of well-structured speeches: the thematic progression of the speeches and its textual elements are logically sequenced. These particular features are transmitted into the TT adequately and with maximum accuracy. These features are strong evidence that the speeches have indeed been carefully transmitted to the TT. These pre-planned speeches in turn indicate a high degree of formality. However, this is not the case for the third speech; delivered primarily in Modern Standard Arabic yet heavily nuanced with Tunisian dialect; the majority of the syntactic characteristics of the speech are not those of a formal text, where Ben Ali seems to prefer a congruent accessible style to a more packed style. The speech actually displays several value judgements e.g.:

This is totally immoral and unacceptable;

وهذا حرام وعيب

These small delinquent gangs; these violent,

هذه العصابات والمجموعات من المنحرفين

Sometimes bloody events

أحداث عنيفة دامية أحيانا

These examples include subjectivity markers which are directly aimed at the reader. The attitude in the lexis revealed in the translation of the last speech further substantiate the ambiguous characterization of the level of formality, which is used to target the emotion of the hearer, the ST uses everyday conversational expressions as well as colloquial style easily accessible to the ordinary Tunisian e.g.:

الاحداث اللي جارية اليوم في بلادنا، ما هيش متاعنا

The events which are taking place in our country are not part of us

ولم أقبل يوما / وما نقبلش / باش تسيل قطرة دم واحدة من دماء التونسيين

I have never accepted the bloodshed of Tunisians.

واليوم نوكد يزي من اللجوء للكرطوش الحي ، الكرطوش موش مقبول.

I say stop using live ammunition. Live ammunition is not acceptable and is not justifiable,

This style is cleverly mixed with expressions which are characteristic of very formal and literary language; this creates a very personal and rather sophisticated style aimed to appeal directly to Tunisians. However, the translation doesn't reflect this complex use of colloquial and MSA combination. The reader of English speeches cannot infer the kind of the mixed rhetoric used by the president.

3.3.3.4 Tenor: Translation Strategies for the interpersonal function

With regard to the interpersonal function, the persuasive tone of the ST is partially preserved in the TT. It must be admitted, though, that the emotive and persuasive element of the ST lost some of its directness, as the attempt to influence the primary audience is somewhat lost in relation to secondary readers (the readers of the translated speeches). This was caused by the change in sender/receiver relationship; the level of formality for example in the last speech had to be elevated. Colloquial lexical items needed to be explained or substituted by equivalent Standard English terms; just as evaluative lexis used is transferred adequately in the TT for example in the following sentence :

واذ حققنا نتائج مرموقة في مجال التعليم كميا ونوعيا هي محل تقدير وتثمين من قبل
الهيئات الدولية والاممية المختصة فان ذلك يجسم خيارا جوهريا ثابتا في سياستنا من
أجل بناء شعب مثقف

Indeed, the considerable results we have achieved in the area of education at the qualitative and quantitative levels, and which have earned consideration and tribute from specialised international and UN bodies, materialises a fundamental and constant choice in our policy to produce an educated people.

3.3.2.5 Mode analysis:

Exploring the textual function involves the logical organization of the ideational and interpersonal meanings of the speeches. The analysis will include a determination of speech acts involved in persuasion and examination of cohesive elements which are detrimental to achieve a quality translation .The following analysis shall focus on the way coherence and cohesiveness are translated with an eye on the emotive aspect of the speeches .

Mode (language as text, the form of communication: orally delivered speech) .Mode refers to the function of the text in the event and includes the channel taken by the language. In the case of the corpus examined it is spoken. Here we are dealing with mode that is characterized as complex since there is a change of mode that is to say the speeches were

written to be read as if heard. The mode of a text is associated with **textual component**, which is realized through speech acts and information structures (mainly the order and communicative use of sentences), cohesion (the way the text hangs together lexically) as well as coherence.

Here the researcher is interested with the communicative use of emotive sentences in performing social actions. The pragmatic meaning of these communicative acts underlies the theory of speech acts developed by Austin and Searle. To test whether the three acts are transmitted adequately or not, the study applies this theory on Ben Ali's last speech:

- The locutionary act of the speech: By definition, the performance of an utterance comprises *phonetic, phatic and rhetic acts* corresponding to the verbal syntactic and semantic aspects of any meaningful utterances.

Phonetic aspect: A delivered speech translated into written English speech.

Phatic aspect: Opening the speech with "In the name of God, the Merciful, the Compassionate", also the use of standard Arabic that is tainted with colloquial Tunisian throughout the speech; however this phatic aspect of using accessible language in the Tunisian context is not transmitted into the translated text.

Rhetorical aspect: the use of persuasive language. (*I expect all Tunisians, whether they support me or not, to back up efforts of appeasement and to reject violence* ونستنى من كل تونسي ، اللي يساندنا واللي ما (يساندناش ، باش يدعم الجهود، جهود التهدئة).the persuasive and emotive aspect of language is maintained in the TT.

- The illocutionary act of the speech: also known as the force of the utterance, in other words real intended meaning. The speech tried to appeal directly to the Tunisian population for calm, assert for the president's mistakes and pledge for a better future.
- The perlocutionary act of the speech: refers to the actual effect of the speech. The speech was destined to persuade, convince and to get the population to remain calm and reject protest.

Analyzing speech acts, stress, intonation and the presence of performative verbs is crucial to determine the pragmatic aspect of a given text. However, in actual speech situations, it is the context which makes unambiguously clear what the illocutionary force of an utterance is; for instance Ben Ali's speeches were obviously a desperate plea for his population to remain calm and that he is willing to execute their demands unconditionally. Translation handles language in use i.e. parole (The Saussurean parole) in other words the translator should consider language as a means to perform social action. In translation it is always necessary to aim at equivalence of pragmatic meaning and if necessary at the expense of semantic equivalence, which is actually reflected in the translation of the speech.

Determining textual features of the ST and TT is crucial for assessing translation quality, since it will give the evaluator insight on the inners and outs of the texts for comparative purposes. Therefore, both ST and TT should be analyzed according to cohesion and coherence. Textual aspect of meaning which is to be kept equivalent in translation has been stressed by (Catford 1965), he considers a text is any stretch of language in which individual components all relate to one another and form a cohesive whole. Hence a text is a linkage of sentences into a larger unit. Among the major features of a given text, the researcher may cite the following occurrences such as:

- Pro-forms : those – الذين
- Substitution: situation – الوضع (refers to protest, turmoil, unrest, agony, frustration...)
- Co-reference: أولادنا اليوم في الدار، وموش في المدرسة، وهذا حرام وعيب لان أصبحنا خائفين عليهم our children are today confined at home; they are not attending classes. This is totally immoral and unacceptable, because we are afraid for their safety

Here the study aims to analyze Ben Ali's last speech and its translation using the realizations of cohesion and coherence. The analysis takes place with relevant examples from the speech.

As a means of communication texts play a very important role, texts serve different communicative aims. The text under examination is a political speech directed to the

Tunisian population, which is a hybrid text that is expressive and operative text. Below is given the analysis of this speech in terms of cohesion and coherence:

In terms of cohesion:

Cohesion refers to the grammatical unity of a text in which different components exist. In order to make a whole structure and unity of components, some elements such as recurrence, parallelism, use of tense, junctions etc are helpful supporting elements.

For example repetition: I have understood you. I have understood you all- وأنا فهمتكم أي نعم أنا - فهمتكم فهمت الجميع Je vous ai compris. Je vous ai tous compris. Within the text recurrence/repetition of such words helps to prevent digression and to focus on the main theme again and again. Another example is Junctions that are crucial supporters of cohesion .e.g.:

وزيادة على هذا كلفت الحكومة اتصلت بالسيد الوزير الأول باش نقوم بتخفيض في
أسعار المواد والمرافق الأساسية (السكر الحليب الخبز إلي غير ذلك) والرفع في
ميزانية التعويض

“In addition, I have entrusted the Government with decreasing the commodity prices and basic services and increasing the budget of equalization.”

In terms of Coherence:

We can define coherence as the continuity of senses in a text. The unity of meaning through the harmony of concepts and relations is emphasized here. What makes a text coherent is the use of related words, utterances etc. This relation is provided when there is causality, reason, purpose, and time in the text. The chain of relations within this speech may be exemplified as follows:

Address Tunisians> confess I have understood you >plea for calm >announce change>enumerate previous achievements and commitment to the country >express sadness to the present situation >plea for calm >reiterate sadness and make it clear that I have understood you >announce change >hail Tunisia.

As is noticed here, all these are related with each other in the text and form a meaningful unity under the topic of the speech.

3.3.3.6 Mode: Translation Strategies for the textual function

With regard to the textual function, the emotive and persuasive style is preserved through maintaining the appealing cohesive and coherent style. The translation is internally coherent and cohesive. For instance the connectors have been respected (refer to cohesion and coherence analysis in 3.3.2.5 Mode analysis) in the TT between the different paragraphs i.e. the structure of the TT is transmitted similarly to the ST, to show the relationship between the different ideas, improve comprehension and achieve a coherent and fluid text. This criterion has been used for the translation of the entire speech, the ideas are explicitly related, which would make the following of the logic of the speech in the TT easier. Hence reflecting the emotive side carried out by the coherence and accessibility of the speeches into the target text.

It should also be taken into account that the translator has respected the requirements of the translation commission; the translator wrote a political persuasive/informative article that is perfectly appropriate for the electronic journal where the article is published. Only by respecting this criterion the translator was able to create a TT that meets the target acceptability criteria. For instance, it is obvious that the translator preferred not to include a paraphrase or any other type of similar resource where he tried to be as faithful as possible in rendering the typological aspects of the speech in the TT. For instance no additional information has been included about the

(decreasing the commodity prices and basic services and increasing the budget of equalisation),

وزيادة على هذا كلفت الحكومة اتصلت بالسيد الوزير الأول باش نقوم بتخفيض في
أسعار المواد والمرافق الأساسية (السكر الحليب الخبز الي غير) ذلك والرفع في
ميزانية التعويض

because in the context where it appears it is perfectly understood that it includes the actually enumerated sugar, milk and bread. To offer more data on these decreasing

commodities would be redundant and superfluous. It has not been necessary to explain this decrease in prices, because this knowledge is not indispensable information for a speech drafted in general terms to an English readership.

3.4 Appraising translation strategies for emotiveness in the speeches

In order to reach an adequate translation strategy that reflects the quality of the TT, the Skopos i.e. the function in situation of the ST has to be compared to the TT Skopos. The translator needs to know exactly which aspects are to be adapted and which are to remain unchanged. It should then be possible to decide on the specific translation strategy/ies, and the requirement for a quality translation. Note that it should be of utmost importance for the translator to know the TT Skopos of the translation. Knowing the purpose of a translation is an indispensable demand for quality. From a translation analysis point of view, the text is challenging to translate in terms of register since the speech was delivered using standard modern Arabic yet heavily nuanced with every day colloquial terminology.

Taking into consideration that the target audience is an educated readership of a prominent socio-political electronic journal published in the web targeting western world, such conditions of translation stipulate that the translator avoid over loose translation and adhere to the fundamental principles of faithfulness, accuracy and adequacy. Hence the challenge is to strike a balance between faithfulness and the over loose translation on the basis of his translation ST-TT analysis. Therefore the translator opted for an overt translation, “where addresses of the translation text are quite “overtly” not being directly addresses, thus it must overtly be a translation and not, as it were, a “second original “(House. 1997:66).

Although the target readership of the TT is western English readers, there should be traces of ST in the TT. For instance president Ben Ali is targeting especially those who are demonstrating and protesting in the streets and the TT is targeting different audience (ambassadors, politicians, western English media ...), therefore functional equivalence cannot be maintained, which is in accordance to the principles of an overt translation. Hence the TT produced is just to inform an outsider of what the speaker of the speech wants to communicate to his population who are angry and furious with the deliverer of the speech. The source text (speeches) aims to inform and influence and move Tunisian

audience to act but the TT would be basically informative for the English readers since they are not the original genuine targeted audience of the ST.

When deciding on a specific translation strategy, we note that the ST profile and the TT profile are almost similar. What has been changed is place and readership and with that a slight change of purpose. As mentioned earlier, the readers of TAP are less informed on matters of Tunisian politics. The English readers cannot be assumed to possess the relevant background knowledge on the politics and culture of the country. The relationship between the speaker and the audience is asymmetrical, where one has much more power than the other.

With regard to the purpose of the speech, the TT is required to give an account of President Ben Ali's attitude towards his population as perceived by (TAP) before the English reader on the same matter. The type of translation adopted can be categorized as an overt translation (see 2.4.3 Source text-based studies; House's TQA model outline), where the translated speeches are embedded in a new speech event which gives them a new frame. Hence an overt translation is a case of language mention as opposed to language use. Noticeably the original speeches and their overt translations are almost equivalent at the level of register (field, tenor and mode) and genre however not function (i.e. functional equivalence cannot be maintained). Therefore we notice that in the TT remains traces of the ST, hence the work of the translator is visible and the TT is marked as a translation.

The textual analysis for emotiveness and persuasion gives a blueprint to the translator on how to approach the process of translation and gives insight to the evaluator of these translated speeches. An in-depth analysis was undertaken to assess the translation of emotiveness to know clearly what is conveyed by the TT. This paved the way to assess the rendering of structures used and meaning of the Arabic speeches in agreement with the ST-TT analysis. The ST and TT have been analysed in detail to assess and gain an understanding of how the major linguistic, textual and sociocultural aspects are conveyed. The analysis of the extra-textual as well as the intra-textual features of the speeches has revealed the way emotiveness is accurately transmitted.

3.5 Summary

The function of the speeches consisting of an interpersonal and ideational component may be summed up as follows: the deliverer's intention is to move people emotionally then

persuade/instruct the addressees to relinquish protest and denounce demonstration in such a way that the emotive-laden speeches presented to the addressees are made attractive, genuine and easily digestible in order to suit the addressees' level of knowledge and be moved by the subject matter. These interpersonal and ideational components are to some extent transmitted faithfully and adequately within the target texts.

This chapter analyzed emotiveness in the political speeches of the then incumbent President Ben Ali with an eye on the phase of ST-TT analysis in translation quality assessment. Data analysis has revealed that translating emotiveness with quality is a challenging task where utmost analysis should be given to ST-TT analysis. The assessor of such discourse should proceed with a register/genre analysis of both texts, from that analysis he can then sketch the strategies needed for the translation of the ST.

In the following conclusion of the dissertation, based on the data analysis carried out in this chapter, the findings along with their repercussions will be revealed and discussed in detail.

Chapter Four: Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that the evaluator as well as the translator of the speeches of president Ben Ali delivered during the Tunisian revolution faced several challenges in transmitting and assessing the interpersonal, ideational and the textual functions of the speeches.

The speeches under examination were deeply connected to the Tunisian context in terms of political terms, social differences and the use of dialectal Arabic. Although there were a small number of cultures bound terms, the speeches were full of value-laden and historically conditioned terms and phrases, such use of language distinguished these speeches making them challenging to translate hence the need of meticulous ST-TT analysis for their assessment (see chapter three).

The study has also shown that to achieve a quality translation of the emotive aspect within political speeches, it is crucial for the translator to proceed with a translation-oriented textual analysis that will serve as a tool as well as an end for assessing the translation of political speeches, in doing so the translator can pinpoint the strong emotive and persuasive aspects of language used, and deal with these in the translation of political speeches.

An aim of the study was to assess how political discourse is translated, with a focus on the emotive and expressive aspects of this discourse. It has been shown that the translator managed to transfer the expressive side of the speeches in parts and failed in others. It is also shown through examples that the use of political discourse analysis as a springboard to reach a quality translation is detrimental in the process of translation as well as in the process of evaluation.

By applying House and Trosborg's quality assessment approach, and identifying the intra- and extra-textual features used, as well as the procedures applied in translations of political speeches, this dissertation has ascertained that the translation of emotiveness is a challenging task which needs a thorough analysis of the ST and TT .The evaluator of a given translation have to produce a genre/ register profiles for both texts that will be used to compare the texts to pinpoint possible mismatches.

The translator of political should be aware of the aspects that need to be taken into account in order to achieve communicatively successful translations. It is not enough to distinguish the meaning of each word in the text, but the translator should also comprehend the different levels of the intended meanings, including the Skopos of the text. The study has shown the crucial importance of recognising tenor, field and mode analysis; where the assessor should be able to recognise register and genre functions of both the source language and the target language. While assessing emotiveness the evaluator should keep in mind that the speaker of the original speeches depends on the shared background with his target audience, while the translated texts must be prepared for a different audience who do not share the same background.

The ST analysis of the three speeches has been undertaken in order to create a deeper understanding of the speeches. The TT register and genre analysis has been defined and compared to that of the ST in order to be able to assess which aspects need to be preserved and which have to be adapted for the TT receivers. The aspects in need of adaptation have been pointed out, while at the same time the importance of rendering as accurately as possible those aspects which do not undergo changes has been stressed.

This study investigated emotiveness in the political speeches by President Ben Ali with an eye on translation quality assessment. Data analysis has demonstrated that translating emotiveness with quality is a challenging task where utmost analysis should be given to ST-TT analysis. The findings suggest that translating emotiveness should be broken down into three steps: First, the translator should start with a translation-oriented ST and TT analysis. Second, the translator should decide to seek an overt or covert translation. On the light of the analysis and translation Skopos, he/she should utilize a set of principles or strategies for generating equivalent genre/register meanings. Third, he or she should employ a further set of principles for identifying which meaning from among that range is most likely to be suitable in the present occasion. The translator should check his/her choice for intelligibility and naturalness to avoid any mismatches. These steps collectively if executed properly shall produce a quality translation. These results are like pixels if they are combined together they will produce a high resolution picture of the TQA model.

Furthermore, translation of emotiveness in political speeches must not involve only an analysis of the intended meaning of the speaker and the figurative language applied in the

SL, but also an examination of the emotive forms, and the figurative devices available in the target language, through the analysis of register and genre as outlined in the third chapter. To achieve quality translation the translator of emotiveness should keep in mind that the speaker of the original speeches depends on the shared background with his target audience, while the translated speeches must be transferred for a different audience who do not share the same background.

“Unlike the scientifically (linguistically) based analysis, the evaluative judgment is ultimately not a scientific one, but rather a reflection of a social, political, ethical, moral or personal stance” (House1997:116). Applying genre/register analysis in particular and political discourse analysis in general, in such study will make it possible to scrutinize and achieve a detailed and in-depth understanding of the ST as well as the TT. It is then possible for the translator as well as for the evaluator to identify potential translation problems that may arise in the target text production to reach suitable alternatives that will eventually lead to a quality translation.

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First speech: CARTHAGE, Dec. 28, 2010 - President Zine el Abidine Ben Ali delivered an address to the Tunisian people on Tuesday evening. [Online] available from:
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Second speech : CARTHAGE, Jan. 10, 2011 - President Zine el Abidine Ben Ali made, on Monday afternoon, an address to Tunisian people which was broadcast by national "Tunisie 7" and "Tunisie 21" TV channels and by public and private radio channels.
<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A8Q9kWT-eV8&feature=related> [accessed 31 May 2011].

Third speech :CARTHAGE, Jan. 13, 2011 President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali delivered, on Thursday evening, an address to the Tunisian people which was broadcast by the national "Tunisie-7" and "Tunisie-21" TV channels and the public and private radio stations.
<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2AQm45CGcHo> [accessed 31 May 2011].

A copy of the recorded speeches can be retrieved from the joint CD.

Appendix:

Carthage speech 28 December 2010(TAP) First speech	
<p>CARTHAGE, Dec. 28, 2010 (TAP) - President Zine el Abidine Ben Ali delivered an address to the Tunisian people on Tuesday evening. Here is the full text of the address:</p> <p><i>"In the Name of God, the Merciful, the Compassionate</i></p> <p><i>Fellow citizens,</i></p> <p>I have been following with anxiety and concern the events that took place over the recent days in Sidi Bouzid.</p> <p>While these events were triggered by one social case, of which we understand the circumstances and psychological factors and whose consequences are regrettable, the exaggerated turn that these events have taken, as a result of their political manipulation by some sides who do not wish good to the homeland and resort to some foreign television channels which broadcast false and unchecked allegations and rely on dramatisation, fabrication and defamation hostile to Tunisia, requires from us to clarify some issues and confirm the truths that must be taken into consideration:</p> <p><i>First,</i> we do understand the feelings of any unemployed person, particularly if his search for a job goes on, his social conditions are difficult and his psychological structure is fragile, which may lead him to resort to desperate solutions in order to draw attention on his situation.</p> <p>We spare no efforts to prevent such cases by providing them with a special and</p>	<p>قرطاج 28 ديسمبر 2010 (وات) (توجه الرئيس زين العابدين بن علي مساء يوم الثلاثاء بكلمة الى الشعب التونسي تم بثها عبر القنوات الاذاعية والتلفزيونية التونسية.</p> <p>وفي ما يلي النص الكامل لهذه الكلمة:</p> <p>"بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم</p> <p>أيها المواطنون أيتها المواطنات</p> <p>لقد تابعت بانتشغال ما شهدته سيدي بوزيد من أحداث خلال الأيام المنقضية.</p> <p>ولئن كان منطلق هذه الأحداث حالة اجتماعية نتفهم ظروفها وعواملها النفسية كما نأسف لما خلفته تلك الأحداث من أضرار فإن ما اتخذته من أبعاد مبالغ فيها بسبب الاستغلال السياسي لبعض الاطراف الذين لا يريدون الخير لبلادهم ويلجؤون الى بعض التلفرات الاجنبية التي تبث الاكاذيب والمغالطات دون تحرر بل باعتماد التهويل والتحريض والتجني الاعلامي العدائي لتونس يدعونا الى توضيح بعض المسائل وتأكيد حقائق لا ينبغي التغافل عنها</p> <p>أولا اننا نقدر الشعور الذي ينتاب أي عاطل عن العمل وخصوصا عندما يطول بحثه عن الشغل وتكون ظروفه الاجتماعية صعبة وبنيتة النفسية هشة مما يودي به الى الحلول اليائسة ليلفت النظر الى وضعيته.</p> <p>ونحن لا ندخر جهدا لتفادي مثل هذه الحالات بالمعالجة الخصوصية الملائمة مواصلين سياساتنا وبرامجنا من أجل التشغيل ورعاية ضعف الحال والإحاطة بالأسر المعوزة وتفعيل التنمية الجهوية عبر برامج استثمارية متوالية شملت كل مناطق البلاد وكان اخرها ما أقرناه في المجلس الوزاري ليوم 15 ديسمبر الجاري وما أعلن عنه من برامج اضافية ستفوق الاعتمادات</p>

appropriate treatment.

Thus, we pursue our policies and programmes of employment, protection of the disadvantaged categories, care for poor families and vitalisation of regional development, through successive investment programmes covering all regions of the country, the latest being those we decided at last December 15 Cabinet meeting and the announced additional programme which appropriated funds will reach 6500 million dinars.

This initiative is part of our concern to meet all attributes of balanced and fair development among regions and ensure fair distribution of its fruits among all categories.

Second, unemployment is a major concern in the different countries of the world, be they developed or emerging; and we, in Tunisia, are straining every nerve to curb it and deal with its effects and impact, particularly on families who lack resources. The State will exert additional efforts in this area during the period to come.

Indeed, the considerable results we have achieved in the area of education at the qualitative and quantitative levels, and which have earned consideration and tribute from specialised international and UN bodies, materialises a fundamental and constant choice in our policy to produce an educated people.

Among these major results, there is the significant increase in the number of university graduates shared out between all regions of the country without exception and whose number exceeded, last year for instance, 80,000 graduates, a figure of which we are proud; in the same way we accept the challenge it imposes for the employment of this high rate of graduates among the job applicants, and this, thanks to the different employment mechanisms and programmes.

المخصصة لها ستة الاف وخمسمائة مليون دينار في اطار حرصنا الدائم على تأمين كل مقومات التنمية المتوازنة والمتكافئة بين الجهات والتوزيع العادل لثمارها بين الفئات.

ثانيا ان البطالة شغل شاغل لسانر بلدان العالم المتقدمة منها والنامية ونحن في تونس نبذل كل الجهود للحد منها ومعالجة اثارها وتبعاتها خصوصا بالنسبة الى العائلات التي لا مورد لها. وستبذل الدولة جهودا اضافية في هذا المجال خلال المدة القادمة.

واذ حققنا نتائج مرموقة في مجال التعليم كمي ونوعيا هي محل تقدير وتثمين من قبل الهيئات الدولية والاممية المختصة فان ذلك يجسم خيارا جوهريا ثابتا في سياستنا من أجل بناء شعب مثقف.

ومن أبرز تلك النتائج التطور الكبير لعدد خريجي مؤسسات التعليم العالي المنتشرة في كل أنحاء البلاد دون استثناء والذي فاق العام الماضي مثلا ثمانين الف متخرج. وهو عدد نعتز به ونتقبل التحديات التي يطرحها علينا لتشغيل هذه النسبة المرتفعة من حاملي الشهادات ضمن طالبي الشغل وذلك عبر مختلف اليات التشغيل وبرامجه.

ورغم الصعوبات التي يطرحها هذا النوع المستجد من البطالة فانه يبقى مصدرا للتفاؤل بالمستقبل تفاؤل شعب متعلم يثابر من أجل الرقي ومزيد التقدم.

ثالثا لقد دأبنا منذ التغيير على تكريس الحوار مبدأ وأسلوبا للتعامل بين سانر الاطراف الوطنية والاجتماعية حول القضايا والمستجدات التي

Despite the difficulties posed by this new category of unemployed, it remains a source of optimism for the future, an optimism of an educated people who perseveres on the path of well-being and more progress.

Third, we have constantly sought since the Change to entrench dialogue as principle and method of communication among all national and social sides on issues and developments that occur.

Consequently, there is no possible way, in spite of our understanding, that we accept the exploitation of isolated cases, an event or a fortuitous situation, to achieve petty political targets, at the detriment of the national community's interests, its gains and achievements, first and foremost, concord, security and stability.

It is not acceptable that a minority of extremists and agitators in the pay of others, and against the country's interests, resort to violence and street disturbances as means of expression, whatever their form is in a State of law like ours. This is a negative and anti-civil behaviour that presents a distorted image of our country and impedes the flow of investors and tourists which impacts negatively on job creation, while we need them to curb joblessness. Law will be enforced rigorously against these people.

Fourth, we reassert the need to respect freedom of opinion and of speech and keenness to enshrine them in law and entrench them in practice; and we respect any position if it is expressed within the framework of law, the rules and dialogue.

The State will strive to find solutions likely to meet job applications which will carry on increasing in the coming years, as it will act in the meantime to further increase wages and household incomes and, in general, improve living standards of all Tunisians.

تطرح أمامنا. ولا يمكن بأى حال من الأحوال رغم تفهمنا أن نقبل ركوب حالات فردية أو أى حدث أو وضع طارئ لتحقيق مآرب سياسية على حساب مصالح المجموعة الوطنية ومكاسبها وانجازاتها وفي مقدمتها الوئام والامن والاستقرار.

كما أن لجوء أقلية من المتطرفين والمحرضين المأجورين ضد مصالح بلادهم الى العنف والشغب في الشارع وسيلة للتعبير أمر مرفوض في دولة القانون مهما كانت أشكاله وهو مظهر سلبي وغير حضارى يعطي صورة مشوهة عن بلادنا تعوق اقبال المستثمرين والسواح بما ينعكس على احداثات الشغل التي نحن في حاجة اليها للحد من البطالة. وسيطبق القانون على هؤلاء بكل حزم.

رابعا اننا نجدد التأكيد على احترام حرية الرأي والتعبير والحرص على ترسيخها في التشريع والممارسة ونحترم أى موقف اذا ما تم في اطار الالتزام بالقانون ويقواعد الحوار وأخلاقياته.

ان الدولة ساهرة على ايجاد الحلول لتلبية طلبات الشغل التي سيتواصل تزايدها خلال السنوات القليلة القادمة كما تعمل بالتوازي مع ذلك على مواصلة تحسين الاجور ودخل الأسر ومستوى العيش بصورة عامة لكل التونسيين والتونسيات.

خامسا اننا نقدر صعوبة وضع البطالة وتأثيرها النفسي على صاحبها ولذلك فاننا ندعو الادارة عند تعاطيها مع الحالات الصعبة الى تفادى أى تقصير في التواصل معها والى احكام متابعتها. ويتعين على كل السلط الجهوية والمحلية أن تتحمل مسؤولياتها في الإنصات الى المواطن والى تضافر جهود الجميع للتعرف على الوضعيات التي تستوجب عناية خاصة لايجاد الحلول لها وللسعي الى الاستجابة الى أكثر الحالات احتياجا أو التي طال انتظارها للحصول على شغل.

واننا متمسكون دوما بالبعد الاجتماعي لسياستنا

<p><i>Fifth</i>, we are aware of the hardships generated by unemployment and its psychological impact on those who experience it. Consequently, we call on the administration to avoid all shortcomings in dealing with these difficult cases and perfectly follow them up.</p> <p>It is the duty of all regional and local authorities to shoulder their responsibilities of listening to the citizens and joining efforts of all to identify situations that require special care to find appropriate solutions and meet the most urgent cases or those whose waiting time for employment has lasted too long.</p> <p>We are always committed to the social dimension of our development policy so that no region or category be deprived of its opportunity for employment and investment."</p>	<p>التموية حتى لا تحرم جهة أو فئة من حظها في التشغيل والاستثمار.</p> <p>والسلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته"</p>
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Carthage speech 10 January 2010(TAP) Second speech	
<p>CARTHAGE, Jan. 10, 2011 (TAP) - President Zine el Abidine Ben Ali made, on Monday afternoon, an address to Tunisian people which was broadcast by national "Tunisie 7" and "Tunisie 21" TV channels</p>	<p>جانفي 2011 (وات) - توجه الرئيس 10 قرطاج زين العابدين بن علي بعد ظهر يوم الاثنين بكلمة إلى الشعب التونسي على إثر أحداث الشعب التي شهدتها بعض المدن والقرى بعدد من الجهات</p>

and by public and private radio channels.
Here is the full text of the address:

**"In the Name of God, the Merciful, the
Compassionate"**

Fellow citizens,

I address you today, inside the country and abroad, following the troubles and acts of vandalism that took place in some villages and cities in a number of interior regions, causing damage to public and private properties.

These violent, sometimes bloody events, which caused deaths among civilians and injuries among security officers, were perpetrated by hooded gangs that attacked, at night, public institutions and even citizens in their houses. This is an intolerable act of terrorism.

Behind these events are certain parties that have sought to involve our students and unemployed youth; that are inciting for unrest and for taking to the street, by spreading erroneous slogans of despair and concocting false news; and that have unethically exploited an event that we all regret and a state of despair that we understand, which took place in Sidi Bouzid two weeks ago.

We deeply regret the casualties and damages caused by these events, and we renew our compassion with the families of the deceased, God's Blessing Be Upon Them, and of the injured. We share with them their

الداخلية.
وفي ما يلي النص الكامل لهذه الكلمة

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

أيها المواطنون
أيتهن المواطنات

في الداخل والخارج أتوجه اليوم إليكم على إثر ما شهدت بعض المدن والقرى بعدد من الجهات الداخلية من أحداث شغب وتشويش وأضرار أحداث عنيفة دامية. بالأمل العمومية والخاصة أحيانا أدت إلى وفاة مدنيين وإصابة عدد من رجال الأمن قامت بها عصابات ملثمة أقدمت على الاعتداء ليلا على مؤسسات عمومية وحتى على مواطنين في منازلهم في عمل إرهابي لا يمكن السكوت عنه.

أحداث وراءها أياد لم تتورع عن توريط أبنائنا أياد تحت على من التلاميذ والشباب العاطل فيها الشغب والخروج إلى الشارع بنشر شعارات اليأس الكاذبة وافتعال الأخبار الزائفة استغلت بدون أخلاق حدثا أسفنا له جميعا وحالة يأس نتفهمها كانت جدت بسيدى بوزيد منذ أسبوعين

وإذ نعرب عن بالغ أسفنا للوفيات والأضرار التي نجمت عن هذه الأحداث فإننا نجد تعاطفنا مع أسر المتوفين رحمهم الله والمتضررين ونشاركهم ألمهم وحزنهم ونواسيهم صادقين. الحب لكل أبنائنا وبناتنا دون فرق ولا استثناء وقد أخذت العدالة مجراها للتحقيق في ظروف وملابسات هذه الأحداث وتحديد المسؤوليات فيها.

pain and sorrow, and we express to them our sincere sympathy.

We also reaffirm our feeling of affection toward all our sons and daughters, without any exception or distinction. Investigations are currently under way to reveal the facts and conditions of these events and to identify those responsible for them.

Fellow citizens,

These events are perpetrated by a minority of detractors who feel offended, anxious and outraged to see Tunisia achieve success, growth and progress, as testified to by all international and UN institutions and bodies known for their objectivity and impartiality.

Those ill-wishers exploited the issue of unemployment, by manipulating an isolated case of despair that can take place in all societies and in many situations.

Those mercenary detractors have sold their consciences to extremist and terrorist parties that are manipulated from abroad and do not wish any good to a country committed to work and perseverance; a country that draws its strength from the intelligence of its sons and daughters.

We have always invested in this intelligence, for we prefer to face challenges and difficulties with an educated people, rather than to seek an illusory security with an ignorant people.

Everybody is aware of the tremendous effort we are making to promote employment which we always consider as our most pressing priority. Everybody is aware of the great attention we offer to university graduates. As I have already stated, we are proud of their increasing numbers, and are

أيها المواطنين
أيها المواطنات
إن هذه الأحداث أعمال قلة من المناوئين الذين
يغيبهم نجاح تونس بل يسوؤهم ويحير نفوسهم
ما تحقق لها من تقدم ونماء تشهد به كل
المؤسسات والهيئات الدولية والأممية المعروفة
بالموضوعية والنزاهة
لقد ركب هؤلاء المغالطون موضوع البطالة
بتوظيف حالة يأس فردية مثلها يتكرر في جميع
المجتمعات وفي عديد الأوضاع، مناوئون
مأجورون ضمائرهم على كف أطراف التطرف
والإرهاب التي تسيرها من الخارج أطراف لا تكن
الخير لبلد حريص على العمل والمثابرة بلد
موارده ذكاء أبنائه وبناته الذين راهانا عليهم
دوما ومازلنا لأننا نفضل مجابهة التحديات
وصعابها بشعب مثقف على الأمان الوهمي بشعب
جاهل

والجميع يعلم كم نبذل من جهود للتشغيل،
التشغيل الذي جعلنا منه دوما وأكد أولوياتنا.
والجميع يعلم كم هي كبيرة عنايتنا بحاملي
الشهادات العليا الذين كما قلت نعتز بأعدادهم
المتكاثرة ونعمل على رفع التحدي الذي تطرحه
هذه الأعداد لأن خياراتنا التربوية من ثوابت
مشروعنا الحضاري والسياسي وإجبارية التعليم
ومجانيته ميدان لا محيد عنهما رغم ما يكلفانه
من ضريبة اجتماعية واقتصادية ونشر
المؤسسات الجامعية في كامل جهات البلاد دون
استثناء واقع ندعمه في كل مرحلة ولن نتراجع
عنه.

إن سياستنا التعليمية مثلها مثل سياساتنا بشأن
الأسرة والمرأة والشباب والطفولة وكذلك ما

striving to meet the challenge they pose.

For our educational choices are among the constant tenets of our civilisational and political project. Free and compulsory education is an irreversible principle, despite the high social and economic costs it entails. Higher education institutions are available in all regions of the country without exception, an irrevocable fact we are consolidating at each stage.

Our educational policy, much like our policies concerning the family, women, youth and children, and the State's efforts to take care of vulnerable segments of society, to preserve the purchasing power, and to subsidise the prices of basic products, which costs the State budget over 1700 million dinars each year—Yes, 1700 million dinars—are a source of pride for us; and we are sparing no effort to further consolidate them, despite our limited financial and natural resources.

Fellow citizens,

Our Programme for the current period, the 12th Development Plan and the specific programme for the promotion of interior, border and Saharan regions, all decided before those events, and the additional programmes we have adopted, are all aimed at addressing the problem of unemployment. They consolidate our ceaseless effort to achieve an equitable and balanced development for all regions and segments of society. They provide jobs and sources of income, give priority to members of needy families, and devote adequate programs for university graduates.

All these policies and programmes do match the policies adopted in the countries of the

تبدله الدولة من جهود للإحاطة بضعاف الحال والحفاظ على القدرة الشرائية ودعم أسعار المواد 1700 الأساسية الذي يكلف الميزانية ما يفوق مليون دينار سنويا نعم 1700 مليون دينار هي من مفاخرنا. ولم نتردد في تفعيلها رغم محدودية مواردنا المالية والطبيعية

أيها المواطنون

أيتها المواطنات

إن برنامجنا للفترة الجارية ومخطط التنمية الثاني عشر والبرنامج الخاص بتنمية الجهات الداخلية والحدودية والصحراوية السابقة كلها لتلك الأحداث وكذلك ما اعتمده من برامج إضافية تصب جميعها في حل مشكلة البطالة وتدعم عملنا المتواصل لتحقيق تنمية متكافئة متوازنة بين الفئات والجهات توفر الشغل وموارد الرزق وتعطى الأولوية إلى أبناء العائلات المعوزة وتخص حاملي الشهادات العليا بالبرامج الملائمة

إن كل هذه السياسات والبرامج تعتبر في مستوى السياسات المعتمدة في بلدان العالم التي تعاني كلها من البطالة فالبطالة ليست حكرا على تونس ولا تونس هي الأسوأ حالا بالنسبة إلى غيرها في هذا المجال. ولم يبق للمغالطين غير ركوب الحالات اليانسة وخدمة أهداف الأطراف الحاكمة والالتجاء إلى الفضائيات المعادية

أيها المواطنون

أيتها المواطنات

إننا نقول لكل من يعمد إلى النيل من مصالح البلاد أو يغرر بشبابنا وبأبنائنا وبناتنا في المدارس والمعاهد ويدفع بهم إلى الشغب والفوضى نقول

world which all suffer from employment.

For unemployment is not specific to Tunisia, and Tunisia's situation in this field is not the worst in comparison with the other countries. Nothing is left for ill-wishers except to exploit cases of despair, to serve the purposes of rancorous parties, and to resort to hostile satellite channels.

Fellow citizens,

To all those who seek to undermine the country's interests or to mislead our youth, sons and daughters in primary and secondary schools and incite them to trouble-making and chaos, we clearly say: the law will have the final say.

We are continuously listening to the concerns of all. We are striving to address collective and individual situations. We are reinforcing our employment programmes so as to curb joblessness, while pursuing our efforts to improve living conditions and quality of life, and to pursue pay-increases without interruption from one round of negotiation to another.

We have decided the following:

First, increasing the employment potential and the creation of sources of income, diversifying their fields and enhancing them in all fields during 2011 and 2012, through a considerable additional effort by the State and the public sector, jointly with the private sector, the banking sector, international co-operation, and all the concerned parties. The aim is to provide jobs to the largest number of job-seekers who are not university

بكل وضوح أن القانون سيكون هو الفيصل.

ونحن نواصل الإصغاء إلى مشاغل الجميع ونسعى إلى معالجة الوضعيات الجماعية والفردية وندعم برامجنا من أجل التشغيل والتصدي للبطالة دون المساس بجهودنا من أجل الرفع من مستوى العيش وجودة الحياة ومواصلة الزيادة في الأجور دون انقطاع من دورة تفاوضية إلى أخرى وقد قررنا ما يلي

مضاعفة طاقة التشغيل وإحداث موارد :أولا الرزق وتنويع ميادينها ودعمها في كل الاختصاصات خلال سنتي 2011 و2012 بمجهود إضافي هام من قبل الدولة والقطاع العمومي وبتضافر جهود القطاع الخاص والقطاع البنكي والتعاون الدولي وسائر الأطراف المعنية. وذلك قصد تشغيل أكبر عدد من العاطلين عن العمل من غير حاملي الشهادات العليا وكذلك من ..بين فاقدي الشغل من كل الفئات والجهات وسيستوعب هذا المجهود أيضا كل حاملي الشهادات العليا الذين تجاوزت مدة بطالتهم عامين قبل موفى سنة 2012 /نعم قبل موفى 2012 وأتعهد بذلك/ وبذلك ترتفع طاقة التشغيل الجمالية خلال هذه الفترة إلى 300 ألف موطن شغل جديد

وكنا أذنا منذ أيام الوزير الأول بالاتصال برجال الأعمال والاجتماع بالاتحاد التونسي للصناعة والتجارة والصناعات التقليدية لحثهم على المساهمة في دعم هذه الجهود بانتداب ما يضاهاى 4 بالمانة من مجموع إطرارات مؤسساتهم من بين حاملي الشهادات أي ما يقارب 50 ألف انتداب جديد في الجهات. وقد لبوا مشكورين دعوتنا. وقد أذنا الحكومة بالمساعدة على تنفيذ هذه المبادرة ومتابعتها.

ثانيا : عقد ندوة وطنية يشارك فيها ممثلون عن المجالس الدستورية والأحزاب السياسية والمنظمات الوطنية ومكونات المجتمع المدني المعنية وعدد من الجامعيين والكفاءات من مختلف القطاعات ذات الصلة وكذلك ممثلين عن الجهات لطرح آرائهم واقتراح التصورات لمزيد

graduates, and also to all jobless people in all regions and from all segments of society.

This effort will cover all university graduates who have remained unemployed for more than two years before the end of 2012 --Yes, before the end of 2012, and I commit myself to it. This will bring the total employment potential during this period up to 300,000 new jobs.

A few days ago, we gave instructions to the Prime Minister to meet with businessmen and with the Tunisian Union for Industry, Trade and Handicrafts, to prompt them to contribute to this effort, by recruiting nearly 4% of the cadres of their institutions from among university graduates, that is, nearly 50,000 new recruitments in all regions. They have favorably responded to our call, and we thank them for that. We also gave instructions to the Government so that it helps with the implementation and follow-up of this initiative.

Second, holding a national conference with the participation of representatives of constitutional councils, political parties, national organisations and the concerned civil society components, along with a number of academics and competences from all the concerned sectors, and representatives from the regions, to present their views and propose approaches, so as to further enhance employment and initiative and meet the expected job demands during the coming years. This conference will take place next month.

Third, giving a new impetus to the regional information by devoting daily airtime on national radio and TV to all governorates of the Republic, while reinforcing the network of regional radio stations and the written press in the governorates, and consolidating audiovisual production units therein, so as to consolidate this qualitative leap.

This will offer more spaces for the

دفع التشغيل والمبادرة بما يستجيب للطلبات وستنظم . المنتظرة للشغل خلال السنوات القادمة هذه الندوة خلال الشهر القادم

ثالثا إعطاء دفع جديد للإعلام الجهوي بتخصيص مساحة يومية بالتلفزة والإذاعات الوطنية لكل ولايات الجمهورية مع تكثيف شبكة الإذاعات الجهوية والصحافة المكتوبة بالولايات ودعم وحدات الإنتاج السمعية البصرية بها لتعزيز هذه النقلة النوعية وذلك بما يفسح المزيد من فضاءات التعبير عن مشاغل المواطنين وطموحاتهم ويواكب واقع الحياة بالجهات

رابعاً:

دعوة نواب الشعب وأعضاء مجلس المستشارين والهيئات المركزية في الأحزاب السياسية الى تكثيف حضورهم بجهاتهم واتصالاتهم الدورية بالمواطنين للإصغاء إليهم والإحاطة بالحالات التي تعرض عليهم وإبلاغها إلى الجهات المعنية للسعى الى معالجتها وإيجاد الحلول لها

كما نجدد الدعوة في هذا الإطار الى المسؤولين الإداريين في المستويين الجهوي والمحلي الى تطوير قنوات الإحاطة بالمواطنين والإصغاء الى مشاغلهم وتيسير طرق معالجة المسائل المطروحة وتذليل العوائق التي قد تعطلها بالتعاون مع المنظمات المختلفة والنسيج الجمعياتي المختص

خامساً:

وعلاوة على كل الجهود التي ستبذل للتشغيل فأبني قررت إعفاء كل مشروع جديد مشغل تفوق نسبة التاطير فيه عشرة بالمائة ويبعث في جهات التنمية الداخلية من الضريبة على الأرباح ومن مساهمة الأعراف في التغطية الاجتماعية وذلك لمدة عشر سنوات

expression of the citizens' concerns and ambitions, and closely reflect living realities in the regions.

Fourth, calling on the people's representatives and members of the Chamber of Advisers, along with the central bodies in political parties, to increase their presence in their regions and their regular contacts with citizens, so as to listen to them and take care of the cases presented to them and refer them to the competent authorities so as to address them and find the adequate solutions.

In the same context, we renew our call to administrative officials at the regional and local levels, to develop the channels of contact with citizens, to listen to their concerns, and to facilitate the means to address their problems and smooth out the difficulties facing them, in co-operation with the concerned organisations and associative fabric.

Fifth, in addition to all the efforts that will be exerted to promote employment, I have decided to exonerate, over a ten-year period, any new job-generating project launched in the interior regions of development and whose managerial staff ratio exceeds 10%, from the tax on profits and from the employers' social security contributions.

On the other hand, we call on parents and all citizens to protect their children from those agitators and trouble-makers, by offering them more care and sensitising them to the dangers of being manipulated and exploited by those extremist groups.

I take this opportunity to renew the expression of my thanks and consideration to my dear brother Muammar Gaddafi, Leader

وإننا ندعو الأولياء وسائر المواطنين إلى الحفاظ على أبنائهم من هؤلاء المشاغبيين والمفسدين بتكثيف الإحاطة بهم وتوعيتهم بمخاطر توظيفهم واستغلالهم من قبل هذه المجموعات المتطرفة. وإنى انتهز هذه المناسبة لأجدد شكري وتقديري لأخي العزيز القائد معمر القذافي قائد الثورة الليبية للمبادرة الكريمة التي لقيت لدى شعبنا كل الارتياح بتيسير تنقل التونسيين وأعمالهم بالشقيقة ليبيا ومعاملتهم مثلهم مثل أشقائهم الليبيين وهو ما يجسم مجددا ما لمسناه دوما لديه ولدى الشعب الليبي الشقيق من صدق الأخوة ووقوة المساندة.

أيها المواطنون

أيتها المواطنات

إن هذه الأحداث لا يمكن أن تغل من عزمنا ولا أن تتال من مكاسبنا بل يجب أن تستخلص جميع الأطراف العبرة منها وأن نواصل مسيرتنا بكل ارادة وحماس لأن عزة تونس ومناعتها أمانة مقدسة لدى التونسيين والتونسيات جميعا "والسلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته"

<p>of the Libyan Revolution, for his kind initiative which has been highly appreciated by our people, which consists in facilitating the movement and activities of Tunisians in sisterly Libya and treating them like their Libyan brothers. This confirms the sincere fraternity and strong support we have always felt on the part of the Leader and the brotherly Libyan people.</p> <p><i>Fellow citizens,</i></p> <p>These events can in no way weaken our determination, nor can they undermine our gains. All parties should draw lessons from these events, while pursuing our progression with resolve and enthusiasm. For preserving Tunisia's glory and invulnerability is a sacred mission entrusted to all Tunisian men and women.</p> <p><i>Thank you for your attention."</i></p>	
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Carthage speech 13 January 2010(TAP) Third speech	
<p>President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali delivered, on Thursday evening, an address to the Tunisian people which was broadcast by the national "Tunis-7" and "Tunisie-21" TV channels and the public and private radio</p>	<p>نص الخطاب الأخير لزين العابدين بن علي قبل مغادرته البلاد بيوم واحد وتنحيه عن الرئاسة</p>

stations.

Here follows the full text of the address:

"In the name of God, the Merciful, the Compassionate

Dear fellow citizens,

I am speaking to you, today, all of you Tunisians, at home and abroad. I am speaking to you in the language of all Tunisian men and women. I am speaking to you, because the situation dictates deep changes, deep and comprehensive transformations.

I have understood you. I have understood you all: the unemployed, the needy, the politician and all those who are claiming more freedom. I understood you, I understood you well. The only thing is that the events which are taking place in our country are not part of us. Destruction is not part of the Tunisian traditions. We, the civilized and tolerant Tunisians.

Violence has never been part of our customs. The present tide of unrest should stop. It must come to a halt, thanks to the combined efforts of all political parties, national organizations, civil society, intellectuals and ordinary citizens. Hand in hand, together, to serve our country, and to guarantee our children's security and safety.

The change which I announce now is an acceptance of your legitimate claims, to which we have reacted. We felt deep pain at the events that occurred, a great pain.

My sadness and my pain are great. I have spent more than fifty years of my life in the service of Tunisia in different positions: from the National Army to the different decision-making positions and 23 years at the presidency. Each day of my life was and

قرطاج 13 جانفي 2011 /وات/ توجه الرئيس
زين العابدين بن علي مساء اليوم الخميس بكلمة
الى الشعب التونسي في ما يلي نصها :

//بسم الله الرحمان الرحيم

أيها الشعب التونسي

نكلمكم اليوم ونكلمكم لكل في تونس وخارج تونس
نكلمكم بلغة كل التونسيين والتونسيات نكلمكم الآن
لان الوضع يفرض تغيير عميق..نعم تغيير عميق
وشامل.

وأنا فهمتكم أي نعم أنا فهمتكم فهمت الجميع
البطل والمحتاج والسياسي واللي طالب مزيد من
الحرية فهمتكم و فهمتكم الكل، لكن الأحداث اللي
جارية اليوم في بلادنا، ما هيش متاعنا ،
والتخريب ما هوش من عادات التونسي ،التونسي
المتحضر ، التونسي المتسامح،

العنف ما هوش متاعنا ولا هو من سلوكنا ،ولا بد
أن يتوقف التيار، يتوقف بتكاتف جهود الجميع ،
أحزاب سياسية ، منظمات وطنية، مجتمع مدني ،
متقنين ومواطنين، اليد في اليد من أجل بلادنا،
اليد في اليد من أجل أمان كل أولادنا

سيكون التغيير اللي أعلن عليه اليوم استجابة
لمطالبكم اللي تفاعلنا معاها، وتالمنا لما حدث
شديد الالم،

حزني والمي كبيران لاني مضيت أكثر من 50
سنة من عمري في خدمة تونس في مختلف
المواقع من الجيش الوطني الى المسؤوليات
المختلفة و23 سنة على رأس الدولة ، كل يوم من
حياتي كان ومازال لخدمة البلاد ، وقدمت
التضحيات - وما نحبش نعددها -بكلكم تعرفوها -
ولم أقبل يوما / وما نقبلش / باش تسيل قطرة دم
واحدة من دماء التونسيين.

تألمنا لسقوط ضحايا وتضرر أشخاص وأنا نرفض

will always be in the service of the country; and I have made countless sacrifices. I have never accepted the blood shed of Tunisians.

We were saddened for the victims of these events and the damage suffered by persons and I refuse to see more victims as a result of the ongoing violence and looting.

Our children are today confined at home; they are not attending classes. This is totally immoral and unacceptable, because we are afraid for their safety, from the acts of violence perpetrated by small groups of bandits, from looting and attacks against persons. This is in actual a crime, not an act of protest. This is immoral.

Citizens should face up to them and we have issued instructions to this end. We rely on the co-operation of all, so that we could distinguish between these small delinquent gangs who are making use of the circumstances and the legitimate and peaceful demonstrations which we accept.

My sadness is great, very deep and great, very profound.

So, I say clearly enough to violence! Enough to violence!

I have also instructed the Interior Minister and I reiterate this. I say stop using live ammunition. Live ammunition is not acceptable and is not justifiable, except, God protects us, if any one seeks to snatch your weapon or attacks you with a fire arm, or compels you to defend yourself.

I call on the independent committee—and I do really mean independent—which will investigate the incidents, abuses and the deaths we regret, to delineate the responsibilities of all sides without exception, with equity, integrity and

أن يسقط المزيد بسبب تواصل العنف والنهب،

أولادنا اليوم في الدار، وموش في المدرسة، وهذا حرام وعيب لأن أصبحنا خائفين عليهم من عنف مجموعات سطو ونهب واعتداء على الأشخاص، وهذا إجرام موش احتجاج ، وهذا حرام.

والمواطنين ،كل المواطنين، لا بد أن يقفوا أمامهم ، وأحنا أعطينا التعليمات ونعول على تعاون الجميع حتى نفرق بين هذه العصابات والمجموعات من المنحرفين الذين يستغلون الظرف ،وبين الاحتجاجات السلمية المشروعة التي لا نرى فيها مانعا.

وأسفي كبير، كبير جدا ، وعميق جدا ، وعميق جدا ، فكفى عنفا كفى عنفا

وعطيت التعليمات كذلك لوزير الداخلية، وكررت ،واليوم نؤكد يزي من اللجوء للكرطوش الحي ، الكرطوش موش مقبول ،ما عندوش مبرر الا لا قدر الله حد يحاول يفك سلاحك ويهجم عليك بالنار وغيرها ،ويجبرك على الدفاع عن النفس.

وأطلب من اللجنة المستقلة ،أكرر المستقلة ، التي ستحقق في الاحداث والتجاوزات والوفيات المأسوف عليها تحديد مسؤوليات كل الأطراف ، كل الأطراف بدون استثناء ، بكل إنصاف ونزاهة وموضوعية.

ونستنى من كل تونسي ، اللي يساندنا واللي ما يساندناش ، باش يدعم الجهود، جهود التهدئة، والتخلي عن العنف والتخريب والافساد ، فالاصلاح لازم الهدوء ، والاحداث اللي شقناها كانت في منطلقها احتجاج على أوضاع اجتماعية ، كنا عملنا جهود كبيرة لمعالجتها، ولكن مازال أماننا مجهود أكبر لتدارك النقائص ،ولازم نعطي لانفسنا جميعا الفرصة والوقت باش تتجسم كل الاجراءات الهامة التي اتخذناها

<p>objectiveness.</p> <p>I expect all Tunisians, whether they support me or not, to back up efforts of appeasement and to reject violence, acts of destruction and degradation of property. Reform requires calm and the events we witnessed were triggered by the protest against a social situation, a situation on which have made huge efforts; but we should make greater efforts to right the wrongs. We should give everybody the possibility and needed time to put into effect all the important measures we have decided.</p> <p>In addition, I have entrusted the Government with decreasing the commodity prices and basic services and increasing the budget of equalisation.</p> <p>Regarding the political demands, I told you that I have understood your message. And this is what I have decided:</p> <p>-Full freedom for all means of information, no blocking of any websites, and rejection of all forms of censorship, while respecting our ethics and the principles of the journalistic profession.</p> <p>-The committee which I announced two days ago to examine the cases of corruption, bribery and abuses by officials will be independent, yes independent. And we will ensure its integrity and impartiality.</p> <p>-From today onwards, there will be full freedom of political expression, including peaceful, guided, organised and civilised demonstrations.</p> <p>-Any political party or organisation can stage a peaceful demonstration. It only has to inform the competent authorities, identify its time and place, guide it, and co-operate</p>	<p>وزيادة على هذا كلفت الحكومة (اتصلت بالسيد الوزير الأول باش نقوم بتخفيض في أسعار المواد والمرافق الأساسية (السكر الحليب الخبز إلي غير ذلك والرفع في ميزانية التعويض</p> <p>أما المطالب السياسية /وقلتكم أنا فهمتكم/ وقررت :</p> <p>// الحرية الكاملة للاعلام بكل وسائله، وعدم غلق مواقع الانترنت، ورفض اي شكل من أشكال الرقابة عليها مع الحرص على احترام أخلاقياتنا ومبادئ المهنة الإعلامية.</p> <p>// أما بالنسبة للجنة التي أعلنت عليها منذ يومين للنظر في ظواهر الفساد والرشوة وأخطاء المسؤولين، وباش تكون هذه اللجنة مستقلة /نعم باش تكون مستقلة/ وسنحرص على نزاهتها وانصافها</p> <p>// والمجال مفتوح من اليوم لحرية التعبير السياسي، ما في ذلك التظاهر السلمي، التظاهر السلمي المؤطر والمنظم، التظاهر الحضاري ، فلا بأس حزب أو منظمة يريد تنظيم تظاهرة سلمية ، يتفضل ،لكن يعلم بيها ، ويحدد وقتها ومكانها ويؤطرها ويتعاون مع الاطراف المسؤولة للمحافظة على طابعها السلمي</p> <p>// ونحب نأكد أن العديد من الامور لم تجر كيما حبيتها تكون وخصوصا في مجالي الديمقراطية والحريات وغلطوني أحيانا بحجب الحقائق وسيحاسبون</p> <p>// ولذا أجدد لكم ، وبكل وضوح ، راني باش نعمل على دعم الديمقراطية وتفعيل التعددية، نعم على دعم الديمقراطية وتفعيل التعددية.</p> <p>// وسأعمل على صون دستور البلاد واحترامه ، ونحب نكرر هنا وخلافا لما أدعاه البعض ، أني تعهدت يوم السابع من نوفمبر بأن لا رئاسة مدى الحياة لا رئاسة مدى الحياة ،ولذلك فاني أجدد الشكر لكل من ناشدني للترشح لسنة 2014 ، ولكني أرفض المساس بشرط السن للترشح</p>
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with the competent authorities to preserve its peaceful character.

-I would like to affirm that many things didn't work the way I wished, especially as regards democracy and freedom. Some have sometimes misled me by hiding truths; and they will indeed be held accountable for that.

-Once again, I wish to say clearly that I will work to promote democracy and pluralism. Yes, to promote democracy and pluralism. I will work to preserve and respect the country's Constitution.

-I would like to say again, and contrary to what some claim. I pledged on November 7, 1987 that there would be no lifetime presidency, no lifetime presidency. Once again, I wish to thank all who launched appeals so that I stand as candidate for the 2014 presidential elections. However, I refuse to violate the age condition for candidacy to the presidency of the republic.

We want to reach 2014 within a climate of genuine civil harmony and national dialogue, with the participation of all national parties in assuming responsibilities.

Tunisia is the country of all of us. We love Tunisia. All our people love Tunisia. We have to safeguard it. The will of its people will be in its hand, and in the hands of the trustworthy hands that the people will choose so that they pursue the progression launched since Independence and which we have pursued since 1987.

To that end, we will set up a national committee headed by an independent national personality enjoying credibility among all political and social parties, to review the Electoral Code, the Press Code and the Law on Associations, etc. The Committee will suggest the necessary provisional approaches till the elections of 2014, including the possibility of separating

لرئاسة الجمهورية.

// اننا نريد بلوغ سنة 2014 في اطار وفاق مدني فعلي وجو من الحوار الوطني وبمشاركة الاطراف الوطنية في المسؤوليات ،

تونس بلادنا الكل تونس نحبوها وكل شعبها يحبها ويلزم نصوصها ،فلنتيق ارادة شعبها بين أيديه وبين الايادي الامينة التي سيختارها لتواصل المسيرة المسيرة التي انطلقت منذ الاستقلال والتي واصلناها منذ سنة 1987

// ولهذا سنكون لجنة وطنية تترأسها شخصية وطنية مستقلة لها المصادقية لدى كل الاطراف السياسية والاجتماعية للنظر في مراجعة المجلة الانتخابية ومجلة الصحافة وقانون الجمعيات. وتقترح اللجنة التصورات المرحلية اللازمة حتى انتخابات سنة 2014 بما في ذلك امكانية فصل الانتخابات التشريعية عن الانتخابات الرئاسية

تونس لنا جميعا فلنحافظ عليها جميعا ومستقبلها بين ايدينا فلنؤمنه جميعا وكل واحد منا مسؤول من موقعه على اعادة أمنها واستقرارها وترميم جراحها والدخول بها في مرحلة جديدة تؤهلها أكثر لمستقبل أفضل

عاشت تونس عاش شعبها عاشت الجمهورية

والسلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته//

between the legislative elections and the presidential elections.

Tunisia belongs to all of us. Let us all preserve it. Its future lies in our hands. Let us all guarantee it.

Each one of us is responsible, from his position, for restoring its security and stability, for healing its wounds, and for ushering in a new stage that lays the ground for a better future.

Long live Tunisia!

Long live the Tunisian people!

Long live the Republic!"

Peace be upon you